

Marine Umweltwissenschaften, M.Sc.

MASTERARBEIT
Spatial Mismatches in Social-Ecological Systems in
Transboundary Coastal Governance

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1.3 Publications and Presentations

Preliminary findings from this research were presented at both the 2024 International Geographical Congress in Dublin and the 2024 Marine Social Science Lecture at Helmholtz Institute for Functional Marine Biodiversity (HIFMB) in Oldenburg.

1.4 List of Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ASSI	Area of Special Scientific Interest
EBM	Ecosystem-based management
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
EU	European Union
FCILC	Foyle, Carlingford, and Irish Lights Commission
FFC	Foyle Fisheries Commission
GFA	Good Friday Agreement
HIFMB	Helmholtz Institute for Functional Marine Biodiversity at the University of Oldenburg
ICZM	Integrated Coastal Zone Management
IUCN	International Union for the conservation of Nature and Natural Resources
LA	Loughs Agency
MSP	Marine Spatial Planning
NI	Northern Ireland
PDF	Portable Document Format
ROI	Republic of Ireland
RSPB	Royal Society for the Protection of Birds
SAC	Special Areas of Conservation
SES	Social-Ecological System
SPA	Special Protection Areas
UK	United Kingdom
UNCLOS	United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea

1.5 Abstract

Boundaries represent the dominant paradigm in modern spatial management. However, two-dimensional cartographic representations fail to capture spatial complexity. Boundaries are not merely lines on a map, they also embody conceptual, physical, and temporal dimensions that fundamentally categorize space, processes or phenomena – among others - into an ‘inside’ and an ‘outside’. This categorization can generate *spatial mismatches*, particularly in cross-boundary spaces. Lough Foyle - shared by Northern Ireland and the Republic of Ireland - exemplifies such a cross-boundary space, where the exact location of the boundary between the two States remains disputed and creates *spatial mismatches*. These mismatches are manifest in the presence of unlicensed Pacific Oyster (*Crassostrea gigas*) trestles along the western shore of Lough Foyle. Drawing from boundary and border studies, incorporating various geographical disciplines, while also engaging with scholarship on social-ecological systems this thesis examines the complex social, environmental and political processes, phenomena and their interrelations that constitute *Lough Foyle Space*. This research is framed by two key rationales: first, that resolving existing *spatial mismatches* would require a formal ‘agreement’ between the United Kingdom and the Republic of Ireland on the precise border location; and second, that borders constrain connections between communities on either side of the border. The findings indicate that, while an ‘agreement’ is indeed necessary to alleviate the existing *spatial mismatches*, the critical issue is not the precise demarcation of the border. What is ‘needed’, is a pragmatic governance arrangement that transcends rigid territorial delineation. Addressing the second rationale, Lough Foyle functions more as a space of connection than of disruption, challenging common assumptions about the fragmenting effects of borders in cross-border contexts. This empirical work gives a more nuanced understanding of boundaries and the associated effects and processes in *Lough Foyle Space*, while contributing to further document the need for a fundamental shift away from ontologies that constrain contemporary governance practices toward management approaches which prioritize ecosystem boundaries over political borders.

“I believe in such cartography to be marked by nature, not just to label ourselves on a map like the names of rich men and women on buildings. We are communal histories, communal books. We are not owned or monogamous in our taste and experience. All I desired was to walk upon such an Earth that has no maps.”

(Ondaatje, 1993, p. 261)

2 Introduction

In 1494, the Treaty of Tordesillas was signed between Portugal and Spain, dividing the Atlantic Ocean into Portuguese and Spanish spheres of influence (Steinberg, 1999). Today, more than five centuries later, in an intertidal lough shared between the Republic of Ireland (ROI) and Northern Ireland (NI), visitors walking along the western shore at low tide encounter rows of trestles used for Pacific Oyster (*Crassostrea gigas*) aquafarming (Ansong, 2021). The connection between this historical treaty and contemporary observations at Lough Foyle¹ reveals a fundamental truth about cartographic representation. As Lehman (2022) notes, “maps act as beings in the world, enabling certain possibilities and foreclosing others” (p. 24). For centuries, human-drawn boundaries on maps have shaped our conceptual frameworks. Lines represent the dominant paradigm in modern spatial management, designed to “foster the enclosure, possession, and management of ocean space” (Steinberg, 1999, p. 254). Yet two-dimensional cartographic representations fail to capture spatial complexity (Peters, 2020). Like the ocean itself, our world is “indisputably voluminous, stubbornly material, and unmistakably undergoing continual reformation” (Steinberg & Peters, 2015, p. 248). Boundaries extend beyond mere cartographic delineations to encompass conceptual, physical, and temporal dimensions (Jones, 2009). And while boundaries can divide spaces, they can simultaneously function as lines of connection (Steinberg, 1999).

Boundaries acquire critical significance when adopting a social-ecological system (SES) approach. A SES approach encompasses understanding both social and ecological systems (and their subsystems) along with the interactions between them, all delineated by boundaries² (Ostrom, 2009). Boundaries fundamentally categorize space, processes or phenomena – among others - into an *inside* and an *outside* (Jones, 2009). However, this categorization can generate misalignments between categories, particularly in cross-boundary spaces.

Lough Foyle exemplifies such a cross-boundary space, where the exact location of the boundary between NI and ROI remains disputed. This contestation resists simple resolution, as the lough's geographical features preclude straightforward compromise in human boundary placement, resulting in persistent political uncertainty - and potential *spatial mismatches*³ - between the two States (Twomey, 2020). Despite this underlying territorial dispute, management responsibility for Lough Foyle is shared between ROI and NI through the Loughs Agency, a cross-boundary institution jointly funded by both States (Ritchie et al., 2022). However, the Loughs Agency's remit does not extend to licensing and regulating Pacific Oyster aquafarming in Lough Foyle, a limitation directly attributable to the disputed boundary location and consequent land tenure issues (Ritchie et al., 2022).

¹ For more details on the history and geography of Lough Foyle, please see *Chapter 4.Methods*.

² For further discussion of SES see *Section 3.3 Social-Ecological Systems*.

³*Spatial mismatches* occur when the spaces of the social systems and the ecological systems and their interactions of a social-ecological system do not align in either Euclidean and/or non-Euclidean space (see *Chapter 5. Results and Discussion* for a detailed engagement with spatial mismatches).

The Lough Foyle region encompasses interconnected geographical, social, and ecological issues. To capture this multidimensional character, I hereafter refer to the region as the *Lough Foyle Space*. This terminology extends beyond the physical water body and catchment to encompass the cognitive and affective connections of its inhabitants, while acknowledging the historical contexts and temporalities within.

2.1 Research aims

This thesis examines the complex social, environmental and political processes and phenomena (and their interrelations) that constitute *Lough Foyle Space*. Transboundary dynamics are generally not sufficiently understood (Laine, 2021), creating a critical need to investigate how social, environmental and political processes - among others - interact across boundaries and shape distinct cross-boundary spaces. Focusing on *spatial mismatches* that form and are formed by boundaries, this thesis analyzes how these boundaries are *experienced, negotiated, and maintained* within *Lough Foyle Space*.

This research is situated within a postdoctoral project on *Social-Ecological Networks in Transboundary Areas*⁴, which compares two case studies: one on the Amazon coast in Brazil and the other in the Lough Foyle region on the island of Ireland. The Lough Foyle site was selected through established research networks and based on specific comparative parameters that enable meaningful analysis between the two regions⁵.

2.2 Positionality

This case study was enabled through affiliation with and funding from the Helmholtz Institute for Functional Marine Biodiversity at the University of Oldenburg (HIFMB) and the broader Helmholtz organization. This institutional connection likely provided certain advantages in my role as a student interviewer. Acknowledging this requires critical reflection on my positionality, recognizing that the researcher is never removed from the research process, and we must acknowledge the impact of the researcher's presence and the inherent power relations this entails (Clifford et al., 2016).

My formative experiences in the border region of Rhineland Palatinate, Germany, have shaped my interest in borders and boundaries. Simultaneously, my academic background in (marine) environmental sciences informed the application of an SES approach to *Lough Foyle Space*. This interdisciplinary foundation enables me to investigate various issues from multiple perspectives. However, my grounding in Germany - through HIFMB affiliation, university education, and lifelong residence - positions me as an 'outsider' to the research site, carrying specific assumptions about local dynamics. One underlying assumption was that crossing the border in the *Lough Foyle Space* would resemble my personal

⁴ This project is led by Dr. Rebecca Borges whose research focuses on social-ecological systems, coastal-marine spatial planning, and protected areas. Here is a selected list of Dr. Borges work: (Borges, accepted, in Review; Borges et al., 2020, 2025)

⁵ See *Section 4.3 Site selection* for further discussion on research site selection

experiences of crossing the German-French border near my hometown⁶. Therefore, I acknowledge my position in this research and, given that this project marks my first engagement with critical social science literature, I recognize that the knowledge produced from this position is inherently partial (Peters, 2017). Or in other words, “my location vis-à-vis my interlocutors’ location shapes how I interpret the empirical evidence of this study” (Saputra, 2024, p. 1).

In reflection of these positionality considerations and to complement literature-based analysis, I have integrated *Reflection Boxes* throughout this thesis. These so-called *retrospective field reflections* provide a “more detailed, more reliable and often more focused account” (Clifford et al., 2016, p. 158) of my research experience while offering readers enhanced contextual understanding. Additionally, the *retrospective field reflections* are drawn from a reflective field diary (for an exemplary page of this see **Figure 1**), which while not constituting a formal method of this study, introduces an important reflexive dimension to the analysis, acknowledging my positionality in examining these multifaceted phenomena (Peters, 2017).

Figure 1: Exemplary page of the reflective field diary used during the research stay in Lough Foyle Space (Source: Author's own).

⁶ Please see Reflection Box 5.1 A Border Experience for further discussion.

2.3 Outlook

My position as an interdisciplinary researcher informs *Chapter 3. Literature Review*, which synthesizes diverse theoretical frameworks underpinning this thesis. The analysis integrates boundary and border studies with various geographical disciplines while also engaging with social-ecological systems scholarship. Through critical examination of existing Lough Foyle research, this chapter identifies significant gaps in our understanding of social, environmental and political processes and phenomena in *Lough Foyle Space*. Although Lough Foyle has been extensively studied (i.e. Flannery et al., 2015; Hughes, 2021; Ritchie et al., 2019), this thesis presents a novel analytical approach by examining this space through a boundary-focused lens. By critically engaging with and challenging established boundary and border concepts, this research bridges a crucial gap between global theoretical frameworks and localized manifestations of boundary dynamics in marine spaces.

Chapter 4. Methods establishes the methodological framework of this research by introducing the study area and research approach. *Section 4.2 Ethics* foregrounds research ethics, emphasizing the reflexive practices essential to this study. The chapter then provides a detailed characterization of *Lough Foyle Space*, encompassing its geographical extent and historical context, while articulating the research team's site selection rationale. The subsequent sections outline the stakeholder identification process, data collection strategies, and analytical procedures. Acknowledging that the collected data exceeded the scope of a master's thesis, this section provides clear justification for the analytical focus. The chapter concludes by describing the planned stakeholder feedback mechanisms, designed to share findings with interview participants.

In *Chapter 5. Results and Discussion*, this thesis provides an in-depth analysis of the interview data focusing on two key concepts: boundaries and borders. The analysis examines participants' perspectives on the importance of establishing an 'agreement' between the Republic of Ireland and the United Kingdom (UK) regarding the precise location of the border in Lough Foyle. Sections *5.2 Multilevel constructions and mismatches in Lough Foyle Space* and *5.3 Borders without boundaries* highlight *spatial mismatches* in the *Lough Foyle Space*. While *Section 5.2 Multilevel constructions and mismatches in Lough Foyle Space* analyzes how the multilevel construction of this space contributes to *spatial mismatches*, *Section 5.3 Borders without boundaries: Pragmatism and the border* identifies two key *spatial mismatches*. With the first emerging between official policy frameworks and lived realities and the second manifesting between the understanding of the border in everyday life and its representation on a map. Furthermore, sections *5.4 Borders, Disruptors* and *5.6 Borders, Spaces of connection* explore different dimensions of borders in *Lough Foyle Space*. While borders can disrupt various human flows and relationships, they also serve as human spaces of connection and collaboration across the dividing lines. Notably, while human activities can be constrained by borders, more-than-human entities remain largely unaffected. This is particularly evident for Lough Foyle, where the dynamic and intertidal environment challenges conventional territorial approaches to marine governance, which tend to rely on rigid, static zoning. Instead, following Steinberg and Peters (2015),

this research employs a ‘wet’ ontology to reconceptualize (marine) governance in fluid spaces. *Section 5.5 ‘Wet Borders’* elaborates on the necessity of this ontological shift, while *Section 5.7 ‘Useful’ Boundaries* applies it to the specific ecological and social dynamics of *Lough Foyle Space*.

To address the identified *spatial mismatches*, this thesis concludes and argues for not replacing national borders - which will of course endure - with ecosystem ones, but allowing ecosystems boundaries to overlap and function across, over and through national borders as the working bounding and management mechanisms of these spaces. Furthermore, this thesis emphasizes that the effective management of cross-border ecosystems necessitates a nuanced understanding of the multiple scales and levels at which these systems operate.

2.4 Research rationales

The analysis of the interview data is framed by two key rationales that guided the research team at the outset of this project. First, resolving existing *spatial mismatches* in *Lough Foyle Space* would require a formal ‘agreement’ between the Republic of Ireland and the United Kingdom on the precise location of the border. Second, borders constrain connections (i.e. personal, social, political and economic) between communities on either side. These rationales are based on the premise that boundaries and borders are distinct concepts, rather than interchangeable terms.

In the following chapter this thesis engages with relevant literature from diverse fields to contextualize these rationales within the *Lough Foyle Space*.

3 Literature Review

This chapter establishes the theoretical framework that underpins this thesis by examining the intersections between boundary studies, social-ecological systems, and their application to Lough Foyle. Through critical analysis of existing literature, this research is situated within contemporary debates on boundaries and borders while developing key concepts that inform subsequent chapters of this thesis.

Section 3.2 Boundaries and Borders, reviews the current state of boundary studies, synthesizing perspectives from multiple disciplines to conceptualize boundaries and borders, their associated processes, and fundamental theoretical concepts. Furthermore, this section extends the current debate on boundaries from its ‘landed’ origins into a marine context and thus showing how current thinking with and about boundaries and borders necessitates a critical examination.

Section 3.3 Social-Ecological Systems then examines the theoretical foundations of social-ecological systems (SES) research and justifies its application as an analytical framework for this study. By establishing the relationship between SES and boundary dynamics, this section provides the conceptual tools necessary for analyzing the interactions within the *Lough Foyle Space*. The section demonstrates how an SES approach offers unique insights into understanding boundary processes in the *Lough Foyle Space*.

The final *Section 3.4 Lough Foyle*, reviews existing research in the *Lough Foyle Space*, specifically focusing on studies that research boundary and border effects. This review situates the present research within current academic discourse while highlighting the novel contributions this thesis makes to current debates.

3.1 Introduction

I am a student of the marine environmental sciences master’s program at University of Oldenburg, an interdisciplinary study program. So, this thesis adopts an interdisciplinary approach: It is based on exploring the management of the marine environment but draws also from border studies, social-ecological systems research, and various geographic subdisciplines including human and political geography. This disciplinary pluralism enables a comprehensive examination of how boundaries are conceptualized and experienced within the *Lough Foyle Space*. Due to the scope of a master’s thesis, I acknowledge the inherent limitations of this time-bounded research project in reviewing all relevant literature, hence positioning it within the relevant fields above.

Lough Foyle, this is important to acknowledge, is not underexamined. It has been the subject of extensive scientific investigation. Regular monitoring programs track physico-chemical parameters, water quality, and dredging activities (*Agri-Food and Biosciences Institute*, 2016), while MacDonald et al.'s (1951) germinal survey established a comprehensive baseline of flora and fauna. More recent studies have examined specific aspects of the system, including aquaculture (Niven et al., 2016),

fisheries (Ferreira et al., 2007), and ecosystem services related to shellfish aquaculture sustainability and carrying capacity (Service et al., 2022).

Management frameworks and practices in the region and across the Republic of Ireland (ROI) and Northern Ireland (NI) have also received considerable scholarly attention. Allen (2010) and Hughes (2021) have explored management challenges, while several researchers (Flannery et al., 2015; Ritchie et al., 2019, 2022; Ritchie & McElduff, 2020 among others) have investigated Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) in the context of cross-border dynamics and the implications of Brexit. While these studies primarily examine how the contested border affects governance and management outcomes, this thesis takes a distinct approach by shifting focus away from the effects of boundaries (or borders), towards how these are *experienced, negotiated, and maintained* in the understanding of the stakeholders. This approach aligns with recent work by Andersen (2024), who examines the “performance and practice” (p. 28) dimensions of borders in Derry~Londonderry through the lens of border temporalities⁷.

Importantly, this research contributes to broader theoretical discussions of *de-territorialization* and *re-territorialization* processes⁸ - that is, the efforts to move beyond ‘landed’ modes of governance (*de-territorialization*), while simultaneously exercising caution against reinstating (neo-)colonial practices of appropriating and enclosing ocean space (*re-territorialization*) (Peters, 2020). These processes, while well-studied at a global level (Peters, 2020; Steinberg, 1999), remain underexamined at local and regional levels. By focusing on boundary dynamics in *Lough Foyle Space*, this thesis bridges an important gap between global theoretical frameworks and local manifestations in (marine) governance. It offers a more nuanced understanding of boundaries and the associated effects and processes in *Lough Foyle Space*. In doing so, it demonstrates that thinking with territorial ontologies⁹ generates *spatial mismatches*. This highlights the need to reconsider current management ontologies of ocean spaces - not only at the global or international level, but also at the local level.

3.2 Boundaries and Borders

Boundaries are complex (Gerst et al., 2018; Laine, 2021; Scott, 2020) in that they are not fixed division lines - they are relative and constructed and thus cannot be split from what Jones (2009) calls the “boundary-making process” (p. 180). In other words, boundaries are made, and remade and in relation to those who live with(in) them. Boundaries are also used to construct categories, and when viewed as containers, we create an ‘inside’, an impermeable ‘barrier’ and an ‘outside’ (Brunet-Jailly, 2005; Español et al., 2021; Jones, 2009; Østhagen, 2020; Peters & Turner, 2025b). And “[b]ecause we cognitively think of categories as containers, we consequently imagine all categories to be inherently closed, with fixed, stable boundaries between them. Yet, intellectually, we know that these boundaries are almost always fluid and permeable” (Jones, 2009, p. 179). In other words, boundaries bound, but they are also always open in various ways. So, boundaries are a relational, multilevel and multiscalar phenomena (Borges,

⁷ For further discussion see *Section 3.4 Lough Foyle*.

⁸ For further discussion of these processes see *Section 3.2.1 A ‘special’ boundary, the border*.

⁹ Peters (2020) defines ontologies as the regimes of what we believe exists.

accepted; Gerst et al., 2018; Hung & Lien, 2020; Laine, 2016) and define a person's understanding of space (Sternlieb et al., 2013).

Thus, defining boundaries is, in many ways, an arbitrary act (Østhagen, 2021). Indeed, by naming the unknown and categorizing it, one "simplifies, organizes and limits the diversity of the world" (Jones, 2009, p. 179). In this way one can create, for example, spatial and functional ecosystem boundaries which impact human and environmental activities (Haselsberger, 2014; Stelzenmüller et al., 2024).

Contemporary boundary scholarship has evolved beyond traditional notions of political borders to encompass a broader spectrum of demarcations, including social boundaries and both material and immaterial spaces (Hung & Lien, 2020; Turner, 2016). Rather than serving solely as barriers, boundaries increasingly function as interfaces of contact and gateways for interaction and exchange (Gerst et al., 2018; Husár et al., 2018; Peters & Turner, 2025b).

3.2.1 A 'special' boundary, the border

The national border, while historically central to boundary studies, has undergone significant theoretical reconceptualization (Scott, 2020). The metaphorical "leaking" of national containers into economic, social, and cultural dimensions (Chilla et al., 2012; Wille, 2024) has transformed our understanding of boundaries, moving beyond their traditional role as rigid state demarcations. This expanded conceptualization positions boundaries as multifaceted phenomena that encompass not only physical and political borders but also conceptual, semantic, and symbolic divisions between categories (Hung & Lien, 2020; Jones, 2009). Yet they "remain fundamental [...] due to their significance in our social and spatial organization" (Turner, 2016, p. 36).

While often used interchangeably in literature, boundaries and borders serve distinct conceptual purposes - borders specifically denote the territorialized, political divisions between nation states (Jones, 2009; Turner, 2016). These borders, and their associated territorial integrity, represent a fundamental pillar of the modern nation state system (Østhagen, 2020). Here, territory is constituted through three interrelated processes: *bordering*, *ordering* and *othering* (Jones, 2009; Peters, 2020). These processes can function as instruments of power (in the negative sense), particularly when deployed through border control mechanisms that reduce individuals to the documents that verify their national belonging (Peters & Turner, 2025b; Scott, 2020). So, borders divide (*bordering*) and unify (*ordering*), exclude and include (*othering*) and because they are made and remade in these processes, they change over the course of time (Husár et al., 2018; Laine, 2021; Paasi, 2018; Turner, 2016).

Although borders are social constructs rather than objective facts, their impact on social realities is profound. These impacts depend heavily on how borders are perceived, experienced, negotiated, and exploited in everyday life, even when the border is far removed (Hung & Lien, 2020; Scott, 2020). While globalization did not result in the predicted erasure of borders (Hung & Lien, 2020), it has led to a complex dynamic of simultaneous debordering for certain interests (such as free trade) and rebordering

for others (such as migration control) (Hung & Lien, 2020; Jones, 2009). This duality reflects what Chilla et al. (2012) term a "selective filter function" (p. 964) of borders.

Borders are fundamental to territorial sovereignty (Chilla et al., 2012; Paasi, 2018; Scott, 2020), and through so-called 'territorializing' practices nation states appropriate and control space as a political technology of the "land, earth [and] ground" (Peters, 2020, p. 4). Beyond initial territorial establishment via *territorialization*, two additional processes emerge: *de-territorialization* and *re-territorialization*. *De-territorialization* refers to the process of transcending traditional cartographic limitations of governance by exploring alternative approaches to managing ocean space beyond two-dimensional zonation. This includes moving past territorial logics which underpin ocean management tools such as MSP or the institutionalized maritime zonation established under the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) (Peters, 2020). *Re-territorialization* on the other hand acknowledges the risk of contemporary ocean governance to inadvertently revert to (neo-)colonial modes of governance and thus can create new inequalities by enclosing and appropriating ocean space and by "defin[ing] problems as they are understood by western science and policy makers" (Peters, 2020, p. 14).

These territorializing practices are inextricably linked to the processes of *bordering*, *ordering*, and *othering*. Specifically, *bordering* emerges as a social process that maintains borders by conferring what Hall et al. (2011, as cited in Hung & Lien, 2020, p. 188) describe as the "power of exclusion" (Laine, 2016; Wille, 2024). While *bordering* operates across various categories (Hung & Lien, 2020), it is most prominently manifested at the nation-state level (Borges, accepted; Turner, 2016). This process serves as a crucial mechanism in maintaining social order and implementing social control measures (Turner, 2016). This last point also links to *ordering*, which tries to "eliminate social instability by categorizing, organizing and controlling diversity" (Jones, 2009, p. 183). The third process intrinsically connected to borders is *othering*. Drawing upon 'western' reasoning, borders serve as both physical and conceptual demarcations that construct and reinforce distinctions between 'us' and the (often colonized) 'other' (Ghosh & Singh, 2024; Paasi, 2018), thus reproducing territorial ideologies and identity narratives (Peters & Turner, 2025b; Turner, 2016). Jones (2009) characterizes the process of bounding as inherently 'inchoate' to underpin that the above-described processes are always incomplete and are "bounding an entity that is lacking structure and organization" (p. 180). In other words, border and boundary-making "happen to people" and thus these borders are part of people's everyday lives and accommodated and negotiated accordingly (Brambilla & Jones, 2020; Scott, 2020).

However, the climate crisis transcends political borders, suggesting the need to think about alternative political, social, and economic processes beyond traditional territorial constraints, especially when it comes to the sea (Kunz, 2025; Turner, 2016). This raises critical questions about how terrestrial border concepts translate to ocean governance.

3.2.2 Management and the marine context

Marine Spatial Planning represents the "dominant marine management paradigm" (Ritchie et al., 2019, p. 214) in the United Kingdom (UK) and the European Union (EU). While thought of as the "appropriate solution, set to provide the joined up, holistic approach to sustainable management of our seas" (Ritchie & McElduff, 2020, p. 230), MSP fundamentally relies on spatial allocation for specific uses through "zones, areas, sectors" bounded by "borders, boundaries and limits" (Peters, 2020, p. 8; Jay et al., 2012; Peters & Turner, 2025b). This includes reiterative processes like the ongoing planning and implementation of marine protected areas (Peters, 2020).

While planning frameworks necessitate fixed boundaries, one should not forget the other dimensions in which boundaries affect spaces (Haselsberger, 2014). The direct application of 'landed' planning methods to marine environments fails to account for the ocean's inherent characteristics - the volume, fluidity and dynamics of ocean and coastal spaces (Jay, 2010; Jay et al., 2012; Peters, 2020; Steinberg & Peters, 2015). So, MSP appears to offer a rational and logical approach to marine management, as this 'works' on land. Although, it should be noted that this constructed rationality is based on a territorial ontology that often serves existing power structures (Peters, 2020). This is especially the case when planning practices have been critiqued for their post-political characteristics, including "the advancement of neoliberal policies, choreographed participation, and technocratic managerialism" (Flannery et al., 2019, p. 204; Peters, 2020).

The complex and often contentious nature of how boundaries are imposed on the ocean necessitates a critical examination of these boundaries and an exploration of alternative approaches to ocean governance (Peters & Turner, 2025a). This raises an essential question: how did we arrive at a paradigm where the dominant approach is to divide the ocean into zones for management?

Historically, the governance of the oceans has been shaped by two opposing visions: the 'freedom of the seas' as envisioned by Hugo Grotius, and the concept of 'closed seas' advocated by John Selden. In contemporary practice, Selden's vision has prevailed, with borders becoming central to the cartographic imagination (Østhagen, 2020; Paasi, 2018). The establishment of global maritime zonation, and the spatial power it entails, was institutionalized through UNCLOS in 1982. This framework introduced key concepts such as territorial seas, exclusive economic zones (EEZs), and contiguous zones, thus enabling states to "extend their control over their proximate seas" (Ryan, 2019, p. 1055; Østhagen, 2020). Initially, the sea was conceived as an extension of land primarily for defense purposes (Ryan, 2019). However, UNCLOS, largely focused on boundary-making, extended the state system into oceanic space, fundamentally altering the "relationship between states and maritime space" (Østhagen, 2020, p. 1). These 'landed' concepts are challenging to transpose into 'wet spaces' and do not 'belong' at sea, because they assume a stability to "erect walls, build fences, insert checkpoints" (Peters, 2020, p. 4; Laine, 2016; Peters & Turner, 2025b). Consequently, they "territorialize the sea through forms of sovereignty and modes of appropriation derived from terrestrial experiences, as nations seek to 'flatten' the geophysical

divide between land and sea" (Peters, 2020, p. 5). Thus, the oceans are undergoing unprecedented rates of enclosure through various bordering regimes (Fairbanks et al., 2018). Three significant global phases of oceanic bordering stand out: the establishment of a territorial limit for national waters (set at 12 nautical miles); the delineation of EEZs for coastal nations (up to 200 nautical miles); and the growing intensification of bordering through conservation practices, particularly in the High Seas (Peters & Turner, 2025b).

Different states have developed varied interpretations of how to draw maritime borders, with the concept of "territoriality" and state rights taking on distinct forms compared to land. The ocean's legal status has changed over time, transitioning from the notion of the oceans as a commons to the construction of static maritime borders under the framework of UNCLOS (Østhagen, 2020). Today, more than half of all maritime borders remain disputed worldwide, as states face significant challenges in reaching agreements during bilateral negotiations. These challenges stem from the political, economic, and symbolic importance of these borders, with states often "leaning on historical, legal, and economic arguments to support their positions" (Østhagen, 2020, p. 6).

Nonetheless, while territory remains the dominant ontology underpinning oceanic control, there are (and have historically been) viable alternatives to the paradigm of enclosures (Lambach, 2020). Unpacking these alternatives necessitates a critical examination of how territorial logics operate in practice across maritime spaces, particularly given that governance at sea often hinges on *where*, *how*, and by *whom* borders are drawn - and in *whose* interests. These acts of bordering at sea often appear superficial, despite the ocean having volume and depth - its governance predominantly demarcates horizontally, yet bordering frequently extends to what lies beneath the surface (Peters & Turner, 2025b). Indeed, when approached from a perspective informed by the ocean's inherent fluidity and dynamism, the potential for alternative zonation becomes limitless, challenging the very concept of static zones (Steinberg, 2011).

In conclusion, borders, though intended to bring order, may make little sense in dynamic spaces like the ocean and can even cause harm. Borders are unrelenting and far from innocent - the involved allocation, and at times, the seizure of space for particular purposes (even for the 'greater good') necessitate to interrogate and examine borders and boundaries critically (Peters, 2020; Peters & Turner, 2025a).

3.3 Social-Ecological Systems

Having introduced boundaries, borders and then discussed them in the context of the sea, this next section takes on the concept of Social-Ecological Systems. This has developed into a mainstream research field, emphasizing the interdependent linkages between environmental and social change and how these linkages influence the pursuit of sustainability goals across various levels, scales and systems (Martín-López et al., 2017; Partelow, 2018). SESs encompass social systems and ecological systems (and their subsystems) as well as the interactions between them (Ostrom, 2009). The precise definition of an SES often depends on the context and focus of the research being conducted (Glaser & Glaeser,

2014). The definition proposed by Glaser and Glaeser (2014) is adopted for this study, which defines an SES as comprising of a biogeophysical area, an identified issue, and the associated social agents and institutions. Once a specific issue and biogeophysical area are delineated, an SES "may extend across spatial, institutional, and other scales, with important feedbacks between the multiple levels of its constituent scales" (Glaser & Glaeser, 2014, p. 2042).

The boundaries of the social and the ecological systems are open, allowing for interactions with other social or ecological systems. At the same time, they are nested, meaning they are entirely enclosed within the boundaries of another social or ecological system (see **Figure 2**) (Glaser & Glaeser, 2014). Moreover, the boundaries between social and ecological systems are socially constructed (Manyani et al., 2024), implying that the definition of an SES boundary is not fixed but instead depends on the specific problem or issue under examination, even when situated in the same geographical region (Glaser & Glaeser, 2014).

Figure 2: Schematic illustration of the three components of a social-ecological system: the social system, the ecological system, and the interactions that link them (Source: Author's own).

SEs operate across local, regional, and global levels. At the regional level, identifying SEs facilitates landscape planning by aligning stakeholder interests with decision-makers. At the local level, characterizing SEs is particularly vital, as planning decisions have direct impacts on ecosystem services and the wellbeing of stakeholders (Martín-López et al., 2017). Glaser and Glaeser (2014) propose that the mid-level of a hierarchical scale offers the most promising focal point for situating research. They emphasize that effective research requires clearly defined SE boundaries to distinguish between the different systems (Glaser & Glaeser, 2014; Ostrom, 2009).

Using Glaser and Glaeser's (2014) definition, this thesis argues that the *Lough Foyle Space* qualifies as a Social-Ecological System. This case study focuses on a clearly defined biogeophysical area - the River Foyle, its catchment, and Lough Foyle - within which a specific issue, unlicensed Pacific Oyster aquafarming, has been identified. Additionally, the study involves associated social agents and institutions, which in this context are the defined stakeholders of *Lough Foyle Space*. *Chapter 4. Methods* will discuss and describe these three core aspects of the identified SE in detail.

3.4 Lough Foyle

The study of oysters and boundaries in Lough Foyle is far from understudied. However, exploring the Lough Foyle Space through the lens of boundaries and borders - focusing on the boundaries themselves rather than cross-border management or their effects - remains relatively underexamined.

Ritchie et al. (2019) demonstrate that MSP has become well-established in multiple layers of governance in the United Kingdom. Their research documents the comprehensive development of primary legislation, marine planning policies, and both national and regional marine plans encompassing the UK's inshore and offshore waters. Despite these advancements, subsequent work by Ritchie et al. (2022) identifies persistent fragmentation within Northern Ireland's governance structures.

Flannery et al. (2015) and Ansong et al. (2022) both further highlight the challenges posed by disputed political and administrative boundaries, emphasizing how such issues can significantly hinder the development of integrated, transboundary approaches to MSP and management.

Andersen (2024) explores how border temporalities continue to shape everyday life in Derry~Londonderry and Northern Ireland, demonstrating how the memory of the border persists despite its current 'invisibility'. Although no border checkpoints exist within the city, the border lives on in the collective memory of its citizens, linking present-day experience to a legacy of past violence¹⁰. This memory often manifests in material forms such as murals and walls - structures that can be erected on land. While this thesis adopts a perspective on borders in the *Lough Foyle Space* similar to that of Andersen (2024) - approaching them as performative and practiced - it also introduces a distinct analytical lens. In contrast to the land-based, static manifestations of borders in Andersen's (2024) Study, *Lough Foyle Space* is conceptualized here as a dynamic and 'wet' space.

¹⁰ For more historical detail on the Lough Foyle Space, see *Section 4.3.2 History* in the following chapter.

While there has been substantial research on how Lough Foyle is managed and how its catchment is impacted, this study seeks to investigate the boundaries within these systems. Existing studies (Hughes, 2021) examine how boundaries influence management and governance. However, they have not explicitly analyzed the study site through the specific lens of boundaries. In these studies, boundaries - particularly contested borders - are often treated as fixed and disruptive elements rather than phenomena warranting exploration.

With maritime space becoming increasingly significant to states, unresolved border disputes may become more challenging to resolve in the future (Østhagen, 2020). So, by adopting a ‘microscopic’ perspective on the interactions with boundaries within this SES, this case study provides a unique and rarely undertaken approach. Examining an issue at such a granular level offers the potential to extrapolate findings to broader, higher levels of analysis. In doing so, this research contributes to ongoing debates on *de- and re-territorialization processes*, providing fresh perspectives and insights into a critical and pressing issue.

3.5 Conclusion

This chapter synthesizes the diverse theoretical frameworks that underpin this thesis, drawing from boundary and border studies, various geographic subdisciplines and engaging with scholarship on social-ecological systems. While *Lough Foyle Space* has been the subject of considerable research, this chapter identifies key gaps in understanding. This thesis offers a novel analytical approach by examining *Lough Foyle Space* through the lens of boundaries. By critically engaging with established concepts of boundaries and borders, this research bridges an important gap between global theoretical frameworks and the localized manifestation of boundary dynamics in marine spaces.

The following *Chapter 4. Methods* outlines the methodological approaches that underpin this thesis, concluding the foundational work of this thesis and setting the stage for the subsequent analysis.

4 Methods

4.1 Introduction

This chapter establishes the methodological framework that underpins this research, presenting a comprehensive overview of the study area and the selected research approach. *Section 4.2 Ethics* addresses the critical ethical dimensions integral to this study, particularly emphasizing the necessary ethical considerations of reflexive research practices. The chapter proceeds with a detailed characterization of the *Lough Foyle Space* as a research site, delineating its geographical extent and historical context, while providing a critical justification for the selection of this site as the focal point of this case study. This is followed by an outline of the stakeholder identification process, the data collection strategy and the data analysis process. Given that the extensive data collected exceeds the scope of a master's thesis, this section also justified the selective focus of the analysis. The chapter concludes with description and reflections of a planned stakeholder feedback event.

4.2 Ethics

Given that this research involved direct human interaction, it is paramount to treat these interactions with the utmost care. In other words, to conduct research with humans (and non-humans), I must take an ethical approach to what I do. This means that I am led by morals and principles when engaging in a specific (research) activity (Peters, 2017). These ethical considerations are prescriptive in nature (Bennett et al., 2017), establishing a normative framework – the ‘what I ought to do’ - that guides interactions with both human and non-human subjects throughout the research process.

An ethical research approach forms the cornerstone of responsible scientific investigation and is codified by institutions in their ethical guidelines. While these guidelines provide an essential framework for research conduct, the ethical validity of research extends beyond procedural compliance and lies in its thoughtful execution and genuine respect for all involved parties. So, it is dependent on the principles, interests and values of the people involved. In other words, ethical research ought to be conducted “transparently and sensitively” (Peters, 2017, p. 71), and be, as Clifford et al. (2016, p. 30) add, “thoughtful, informed and reflexive”.

This mindful research is crucial, as this research directly involves the livelihoods of people living in the areas being studied (Bennett, 2019). As researcher, I have “moral, pragmatic, and legal obligations to protect participants from harm” (Brittain et al., 2020, p. 926). Furthermore, researchers often rely on non-academic forms of knowledge to produce academic knowledge (Choy et al., 2009) and therefore, our research should “aim to maximize benefits for individuals and society and minimize risk and harm” (Peters, 2017, p. 85).

Ethical considerations are essential in the planning stage of research, to avoid perpetuating knowledge inequities through “linear flows of colonial and related governance practices” (Muhl et al., 2023, p. 12). It is “morally right to consider ethics” (Brittain et al., 2020, p. 927) at the earliest stages of research

planning. However, this ethical mindfulness must extend beyond planning and be maintained throughout all stages of research to ensure participants' data security, data sovereignty, and the protection of their intellectual property, among others (Muhl et al., 2023; Peters, 2017).

Ethical research also requires thoughtful reflection on the potential consequences of scientific work. I must critically examine whether it is appropriate to pursue research on a particular phenomenon simply because I have the ability to do so. The 'objectivity of science' does not protect me from the risk of reinforcing historical injustices or existing privileges or power relations (Brittain et al., 2020; Peters, 2017). Moreover, I must scrutinize the outcomes of my research, asking where, what, how and for whom I publish my findings, as this can amplify certain discourses while marginalizing others (Muhl et al., 2023; Siriwardane-de Zoysa et al., 2023).

In this project, ethical considerations were integrated into every stage of the research, adhering to the ethical guidelines set by the Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg¹¹. However, I aimed to go beyond these guidelines, recognizing that codified research ethics can contain "immense gaps" (Siriwardane-de Zoysa et al., 2023, p. 173) or "institutional and scholarly cracks" (Brittain et al., 2020, p. 927).

Even though, the research site and the general methodology of this project were predetermined when I joined this project in April 2023 (see *Chapter 2. Introduction*), ethical considerations were carefully deliberated from the outset. Consequently, my ethical focus for this thesis centered on participant selection and my approach to participant engagement. Once contact was established, I ensured that our interactions were open, honest, and transparent throughout. For me, maintaining high ethical standards in this research was a top priority, whereas in other studies, this might take a secondary role (Muhl et al., 2023). I achieved this by providing participants with regular updates and ensuring their confidentiality and anonymity both during and after the interviews. Interviews were only conducted after participants gave informed consent, with clear communication that participation was voluntary and could be withdrawn at any time, even after the interviews were completed (Peters, 2017). Consent was confirmed through signed declaration of consent forms before the interviews began¹². Owing to the historical and political context of the research area¹³, the lines of inquiry necessitated a careful and mindful approach to the interview process and participant engagement.

The anonymity of the participants was particularly important, as the potential impact of this research on their well-being is difficult to anticipate, for I am an outsider to the research area (Brittain et al., 2020; Peters, 2017). At the conclusion of this project, I also considered it essential to provide feedback to the participants through an event I termed 'Retribution Event' (for a critical examination of this term, see *Reflection box 4.6 'Retribution Event'*).

¹¹ The ethics approval of the Commission for Research Impact Assessment and Ethics of the University of Oldenburg can be found in the Appendix.

¹² The Declaration of Consent Form can be found in the Appendix.

¹³ Further discussion is provided in Section 4.3.2 History

For more ethical considerations, please refer to *Reflection box 4.1 Ethics* below.

Reflection box 4.1 Ethics

Ethical considerations remained at the forefront throughout this research process. Ethical deliberations included the appropriate extent of stakeholder follow-up communication with Pacific Oyster aquafarmers¹⁴, the conceptualization and implementation of a feedback event¹⁵ and the amendment to our existing ethics approval to ensure that this event aligned with institutional ethical guidelines.

While I, as researcher, am called upon to examine phenomena through multiple perspectives (Gezon & Paulson, 2020), the question of how one's positionality influences data interpretation requires careful consideration. Or to put in other words, can I, considering my positionality, examine the data this study generated fairly¹⁶ (Peters, 2017)?

These ethical considerations represent select examples from ongoing discussions and reflections that informed the project's ethical framework and should not be considered as a complete list of ethical considerations.

4.3 Site selection

This case study is embedded in the larger postdoctoral project on *Social-ecological Networks in Transboundary Areas* with two research sites (see *Chapter 2. Introduction*). To be able to compare the two case studies with each other we were looking for a baseline of features that the research sites share. Namely, they are placed in a cross-border coastal area, with stakeholders present on each side of the border, hereby the level of the spatial scale on which the border exists (local, regional, national, international) is not a critical factor. The jurisdiction of the ecosystem should differ depending on where exactly you are in the ecosystem. Thus, there would be more than one management framework for the entire ecosystem and the role of borders but also boundaries would be prominent. Additionally, these areas suffer from land tenure issues. The totality of the features would make these areas susceptible to - our essential research interest of - spatial mismatches.

4.3.1 Description of the research site

The second case study of the project, then, and the primary focus of this thesis, is Lough Foyle, where the aforementioned features are evident, as I present in this section, and established research networks were available.

¹⁴ While I find it important that the voices of the aquafarmers are heard in this project, their refusal to participate may have other reasons than presented here in this thesis (Siriwardane-de Zoysa et al., 2023)

¹⁵ Can the way we present the data, even though generalized and anonymous, fully safeguard us against identifying any participant?

¹⁶ *Retrospective field reflection*: "Inside this exhibition [on the 'Troubles'] I immediately took sides with the republican side" (Reflective field diary)

Located in the north-west of the island of Ireland (see **Figure 3** **Figure 3**), Lough Foyle is a shallow sea lough or a ‘semi-enclosed coastal embayment’ (Twomey, 2020, p. 171), surrounded by the counties Derry~Londonderry (Northern Ireland (NI)) and Donegal (Republic of Ireland (ROI)) on the Inishowen Peninsula (see **Figure 4** **Figure 4**). Lough Foyle covers an area of approximately 179 km², is roughly 26 km long and up to 16 km wide, with its narrowest points at the southwestern and the north-eastern ends. Areas of the lough have European Union (EU) and United Kingdom (UK) (marine) protected areas designations, namely Special Protection Areas (SPA), Special Areas of Conservation (SAC), Ramsar site and Area of Special Scientific Interest (ASSI). A dredged navigation channel near the western shore (ROI) is the deepest part of Lough Foyle with a maximum of 15 meters and the average depth is 5 meters (see **Figure 4** **Figure 4**). At low tide 20 % of Lough Foyle area is covered by intertidal mudflats and it supports a wide range of species, especially shellfish (Ansong, 2021; Hughes, 2021; Twomey, 2020).

Figure 3: Location of Lough Foyle on the Island of Ireland (Source: Author's own).

Figure 4: Lough Foyle with the surrounding counties and the location of the navigation channel (Source: Twomey (2020)).

Lough Foyle's catchment of 3700 km² is shared by Northern Ireland and the Republic of Ireland and is one of the largest catchments of all the Irish sea loughs. Due to this inflow of freshwater and its semi-enclosed shape, Lough Foyle has a moderate salinity, with a gradual increase towards the northeast (Ansong, 2021; Hughes, 2021; Twomey, 2020).

Several medium and larger sized towns have a connection to Lough Foyle with the largest being Derry~Londonderry (NI) at the estuary head of the River Foyle. Due to its usage, Lough Foyle has several source points of pollution of its waters, e.g. DuPont chemical complex in Derry~Londonderry and the discharge of untreated wastewater from Moville (ROI) on the Inishowen Peninsula, which in turn affects the water quality and potentially its habitats and species (Ansong, 2021).

Lough Foyle represents not only a hydrological feature but also a crucial ecosystem that has sustained diverse biotic communities, including human populations, for millennia (Campbell, 2021). These communities combined with Lough Foyle's geographical features form a social-ecological system (SES) (see *Chapter 3. Literature Review*) and thus generates emergent meanings beyond the site's physical characteristics (Schlüter et al., 2019).

In the ecological system, Lough Foyle provides an ecosystem for many different species, including plant and animal species on the Red List of the International Union for the conservation of Nature and Natural Resources (IUCN). A survey in the 1930s documented over 118 species of molluscs and another survey in 1982 discovered that Lough Foyle had the largest number of Blue Mussels (*Mytilus edulis*) of any other Irish estuary. But not only aquatic or marine beings are dependent on Lough Foyle. It also is of high importance to migratory birds and, including its mud flats and surrounding salt marshes, it supports

up to 40,000 individuals each winter. In some cases, this covers up to 18 % of the international population (Light- Bellied Brent Goose, *Branta bernicla hrota*) (Ansong, 2021; Twomey, 2020). As mudflats are generally carbon sinks, Lough Foyle's mudflats are a part of the global carbon cycle. Their conservation is important in the efforts of mitigating anthropogenic climate change by sequestering carbon (Chakraborty et al., 2023).

Lough Foyle also affects many aspects of the social system. Economically, Lough Foyle's waters are used as fisheries for various species, with historical fisheries including oyster, mussel and salmon but also other fisheries having developed more recently. The harvested wild mussels are landed in the ports of Greencastle and Moville (both ROI) and from there distributed further to local and European markets. Thus, from a socio-economic perspective, fishing in this region is 30 times more important to the local economy of Lough Foyle than fishing is of importance to Ireland as a whole (Twomey, 2020). However, with Brexit unfolding, access to the two ports has been restricted to fishing boats registered in Northern Ireland. Furthermore, Lough Foyle's importance to the economic aspect of the SES also includes marine and coastal tourism (cruise shipping at Lisahally Docks in Derry~Londonderry, kayaking and angling, for example) and with Foyle Port at the mouth of Foyle River being the largest bulk cargo port in the northwest of Ireland it supports up to 21,000 direct and indirect jobs (Ansong, 2021; Twomey, 2020).

Lough Foyle presents a complex (geo)political landscape within the SES, characterized by the cross-border nature of the lough and a multi-agency and thus fragmented management approach (Ritchie 2022). Both the Republic of Ireland and Northern Ireland, a devolved administration of the UK, lay claim to its ownership and thus leave an undefined border. This opens a gap in the ability to manage the lough in all aspects, as it facilitates unlicensed aquaculture of Pacific Oysters (*Magallana gigas*). Even with the pitfalls when managing the aquaculture, it is an innovative example of establishing a cross-border management entity, the Loughs Agency (Campbell, 2021). In 2020, with Brexit unfolding, Northern Ireland became the only land border between an EU state and the UK, where Lough Foyle, with Carlingford Lough, represent the extension of this border from the terrestrial into the marine space (Ansong, 2021; Twomey, 2020).

The communities around Lough Foyle depend on the lough for their livelihood. With the port as source of employment, its mudflats have not only an ecological importance to migratory birds but also economic value when being used for the trestles of Pacific Oyster aquaculture. It has cultural heritage, including the meaning this provides ('sense of place'), and is a place for recreation, be it water activities (e.g. kayaking on its waters) or the "Foyle Valley Greenway" (Campbell, 2021; *Foyle Valley Cycle Route*, n.d.; Twomey, 2020). All these aspects turn Lough Foyle into a place of connection, where geopolitical borders divide.

4.3.2 History

When describing Lough Foyle, one should not omit the history of the area, and of the two nations involved. To understand the social system of the SES in Lough Foyle it is crucial to understand its

history and the role which history plays, as decisions made in Northern Ireland today maintain strong connections to the decision-making history in the UK (Ansong, 2021). The livelihood of communities on Lough Foyle has relied on its rich fisheries for centuries, historically salmon is important here.

In 1613 the ownership of the fishing rights on Lough Foyle were obtained by the *Honourable Irish Society* as part of the colonization process called the Plantation of Ulster (Ansong, 2021). The partition of Ireland in 1920 established a Southern (later Republic of Ireland) and a Northern Ireland, but failed to delineate marine borders, as it was expected that both administrations would stay part of the UK. With the ROI later severing constitutional links to the UK it became unclear where the territorial waters of the two nations met (Flannery et al., 2015; Ritchie et al., 2019). The disputes took on a new significance in the 1930s and 1940s, when this ambiguity of management led to the poaching of salmon and subsequently to the joint and complementary Foyle Fisheries Acts of 1952, which established the *Foyle Fisheries Commission* (FFC) to “manage, conserve, protect and improve the fisheries” (Hughes, 2021, p. 8) of Lough Foyle and its catchment (Ansong, 2021; Campbell, n.d.).

The FFC was staffed by people from both ROI and NI and oversaw the purchase of the fishing rights from the Honourable Irish Society by the governments of the two nations (Hughes, 2021). From the late 1960s until the signing of the Good Friday Agreement (GFA) in 1998 the violent armed conflict in Northern Ireland known as ‘the Troubles’ was at its highest intensity. During this time the ROI continued to claim all territorial waters around the island until an associated referendum of the GFA amended two articles of the constitution and thus reneged its constitutional claim to all waters around the island and giving way to a notional international marine border (Ansong, 2021).

With the GFA the FFC was transformed into the *Loughs Agency* (LA) and the *Foyle, Carlingford, and Irish Lights Commission* (FCILC). These two bodies have unique cross-border remits in regards to fisheries, navigation and safety, and marine tourism. (Ansong, 2021; Ritchie et al., 2019; Twomey, 2020). Even though the UK government lays claim to the whole of Lough Foyle, the ROI government rejects this claim (Seanad Eireann, 2006). This ambiguity of ownership blocked the way for the LA to be “the aquaculture licensing authority” (Hughes, 2021, p. 9) which the legislation proposed.

In 2007 joint legislation was decided on in the UK and the ROI, the Foyle and Carlingford Fisheries (Northern Ireland) Order 2007 and the Foyle and Carlingford Fisheries Act 2007, respectively. This legislation gives the LA additional remits to protect and manage the Lough Foyle fisheries. And even though this legislation has been partly brought into force, the sections which regulate aquaculture are outstanding due to the disputed ownership of Lough Foyle’s estuary, seabed and foreshore (Hughes, 2021). Further consequence of this dispute is the increase of amount of unlicensed oyster trestles from approximately 2500 in 2010/11 to approximately 50,000 in 2018 and the issues this entails (Ansong, 2021). In conclusion, the historical failure of delineating the border on Lough Foyle in 1920 has had an impact on the gaps in legislation today, more than 100 years later (see **Figure 5**).

Figure 5: Timeline of key historic events concerning the disputed state of Lough Foyle with the accompanying geopolitical regimes above (Source: Ansong 2021)

4.3.3 Where Boundaries Blur: Lough Foyle as a Transboundary Research Opportunity

The juxtaposition of the above factors positions *Lough Foyle Space* as a particularly compelling research site, because it is a biogeographical unit under the jurisdiction of two States, has a history of disputed ownership, the longevity of this dispute (1920 until today) and the various perspectives on territorial claims and the boundaries this creates (Twomey, 2020). Additionally, Lough Foyle is a cross-border sea lough, which has flows and communication or collaboration across an international border and on different jurisdictional levels (local, regional, national and international). The presence of a multiplicity of boundaries - e.g. international borders, physical boundaries and other more abstract boundaries - adds to the potential secondary conflicts this entails. Also, the different types of spatiality, e.g. the high-water mark, the water column and the volume of Lough Foyle, make it a complex and interesting space to research how the different system of the SES interact with noticeable and visual expression – the oyster trestles - of the effects mismatches have therein.

Reflection box 4.2 Field Work

I conducted in-person interviews in Derry~Londonderry over a two-week period spanning August and September 2023. Accommodation was secured in a shared residence in an area of the city locally known as Cityside, on the west bank of the River Foyle. This location, approximately 30 minutes' walking distance from both the central bus station and city center, facilitated primarily pedestrian mobility, supplemented by public transportation (bus and rail) when necessary. While this brief research stay provided valuable insights, it is important to acknowledge its temporal limitations in fully capturing the complexities of this historically rich urban environment where past events continue to shape contemporary life¹⁷ (see *Section 4.3.2 History*).

The River Foyle divides Derry~Londonderry into two distinct areas: Cityside on the western bank and Waterside on the eastern bank. While geographically proximate, these districts reflect observable differences in spatial and social characteristics that suggest two distinct urban environments within the same city¹⁸. Despite evident political-spatial divisions within Derry~Londonderry, my field observations gave me the feeling of cross-community solidarity, particularly in local responses to centralized governance decisions¹⁹. This suggests a complex interplay between internal divisions and shared civic interests.

¹⁷ *Retrospective field reflection*: “Conflict has a feeling of being ongoing under the surface” (quote from field diary), but there are different understandings of this feeling.

¹⁸ *Retrospective field reflection*: The distinct character of these districts is reflected in their visual political symbolism: Waterside prominently displays Union flags, while Cityside features Republican murals and symbolism. The geographical and social division is further illustrated by an anecdotal account of a resident who reportedly first crossed the river only after the construction of the Peace Bridge in 2011, suggesting the persistence of spatial boundaries in residents’ lived experience.

¹⁹ *Retrospective field reflection*: “[...] a history that has shaped people in a ‘don’t-take-anything’ way regarding oppression” (quote from field diary)

Beyond data collection, the field research emphasized relationship-building with stakeholders, aligning with Peters' (2017) advocacy for transparent and democratic research practices. This immersive approach facilitated critical self-reflection and the challenging of preconceptions, thereby enriching the study's analytical framework. The dual process of observing both the research site and examining my own positionality generated valuable insights for both the current study and future methodological considerations.

Critical methodological reflections emerged from this field research, particularly regarding research design elements such as temporal parameters (visit duration and seasonal timing), depth of preliminary literature research, and the logistical considerations of accommodation and interview site (see *Reflection box 4.4 Data collection*). Due to personal constraints, the research stay was limited to a two-week period in late August and early September, which coincided with the traditional summer holiday season in Derry~Londonderry, potentially affecting participant availability and institutional operations. Additionally, the selected accommodation lacked dedicated workspace facilities, which posed minor logistical challenges to data organization and preliminary analysis during the fieldwork period.

4.4 Stakeholder identification

In this study, I took an inclusive approach to stakeholder identification in which I considered every interested party or social actor (or private individual) to be a stakeholder who is “a person, organization or group with an interest [...] or an influence on the marine environment or who is influenced directly or indirectly by activities and management decisions” (Newton & Elliott, 2016, p. 2) on Lough Foyle. Although I did not categorize stakeholders before approaching them in this study, I did systematically search for counterparts across the border. As an example, when I identified the Royal Society for the Protection of Birds (**RSPB**) as a potential participant group I explored analogous organizations in the Republic of Ireland.

Also, the operational level of the organization (local, regional, national, international) was not a limiting factor in our selection criteria, provided they demonstrated a direct connection to Lough Foyle. I, however, searched specifically for organizations of Pacific Oyster aquafarmers, as their trestles epitomize the mismatches central to our research rationales.

The stakeholder identification process commenced with an initial meeting with a local researcher intimately familiar with the study area through their own investigations. After this meeting I had an initial key stakeholder list and a stakeholder database²⁰ was developed from this initial list and subsequently expanded through literature review and online research prior to contacting the first potential participants. Contact information of these stakeholders was obtained solely through publicly available data, e.g. organization websites or public social media profiles. This database underwent continuous refinement throughout the study (or an ad hoc approach as described in the BiodivERsA

²⁰ The stakeholder spreadsheet was omitted to preserve participant anonymity.

Stakeholder Engagement Handbook (Durham et al., 2014)), reflecting new insights gained from in-person interviews - particularly during the social network survey component - and ongoing literature analysis and contact information was obtained as above.

A note of interest here is that my attempts to engage with Pacific Oyster aquafarmers were met with limited success. Despite multiple outreach efforts only one organization responded, which ultimately declined our request for an interview. For thoughts on this see *Reflection box 4.3 Stakeholder identification* below.

My stakeholder engagement process began with the distribution of initial contact emails in July of 2023. These emails provided a brief overview of the project, introduced the research team and the Marine Governance working group at Helmholtz Institute for Functional Marine Biodiversity at the University of Oldenburg, and included a custom-designed infographic²¹ created using Canva (*Canva*, n.d.) to summarize key elements of our project.

To maximize response rates, I implemented a follow-up protocol. Non-responsive stakeholders were sent reminder emails 4-6 weeks after the initial contact.

The engagement strategy was collaboratively developed with my research partner, designed to be both informative and accessible, combining visual communication tools alongside traditional text-based information. This multimodal approach aimed to cater to diverse stakeholder preferences and enhance comprehension of our research objectives.

Reflection box 4.3 Stakeholder identification

Although my stakeholder identification approach was inclusive, I focused solely on organizations due to their publicly available contact information, which social actors typically lack. In future research, as understanding and trust within the area and stakeholders deepens, it may become feasible to engage directly with private individuals as well.

While I reached out to more organizations than those that ultimately responded or agreed to participate in an interview, several contacted organizations - although active in Northern Ireland or the Republic of Ireland – did not consider themselves stakeholders in the context of Lough Foyle and, in some cases, they referred us to the Loughs Agency. Additionally, I was unable to interview all the stakeholders whose perspectives I believe would have provided valuable insights (e.g. Pacific Oyster aquafarming companies).

Among the Pacific oyster aquafarming companies I contacted, only one responded, indicating that they were not currently interested in a discussion. I believe that establishing these conversations would require building a level of trust within the community of oyster aquafarmers to avoid being perceived as an 'outsider', who potentially questions the legality of their livelihoods, given their position in a legal

²¹ The Infographic can be found in the Appendix

grey area (Ansong, 2021). Stakeholders may also be more inclined to engage when they wish to communicate publicly, as Non Government Organizations and various agencies often seek visibility, especially given my affiliation with the prestigious Helmholtz Group. In contrast, most pacific oyster aquafarming companies, with few exceptions (McGinty, 2021), prefer not to provide public comments. Finally, having a surname common in the region may have provided me with an 'edge' in securing participants' willingness to engage in conversation (see *Section 2.2 Positionality*).

4.5 Data collection

This study employed a mixed-methods research design, incorporating multiple data collection techniques to obtain both qualitative and quantitative datasets. The primary data collection method employed was semi-structured interviews with open-ended questions. This approach was selected to gain in-depth insights into participant's understanding of the themes and allows them to describe the matter at hand in their own words, effectively creating what Peters (2017, p. 185) terms a "conversation with a purpose". Simultaneously, the semi-structured format provided a standardized framework across all interviews, enhancing comparability (Peters, 2017; Twomey, 2020). This method was particularly advantageous as it maximized the depth of insight from each interview given the study's limited sample size (see below).

Qualitative data - derived from interviews for example - can serve to complement quantitative methods like surveys or statistical analyses, though its utility extends beyond mere supplementation. Crucially, qualitative methods facilitate the exploration of multifaceted perspectives when examining complex phenomena within social-ecological systems. As Twomey, (2020, p. 115) notes, these methods provide "microscopic details of the social and cultural aspects of the subjects under investigation," allowing for a nuanced understanding of the research context (Ansong, 2021).

The second methodological component involved the construction and analysis of a social network²² of stakeholders specific to Lough Foyle. This approach was implemented to identify key stakeholders within the research area and can uncover *who* affects or is affected by management measures in Lough Foyle and *how* the *whos* connect. The resulting network data facilitates the application of social network theory to understand this network and assess how flows and boundaries shape the social network and whether it might constrain or enable key social processes in Lough Foyle (Guerrero et al., 2013).

The third methodological component integrated a participatory mapping exercise into the interview schedule to gain insights into the value and importance of Lough Foyle for the participants (Strickland-Munro et al., 2015). With the participatory process I sought to fully engage with the participant and to dissolve the distinguishment between the researcher and the researched. Additionally, with this

²² Networks of formal or informal relationships that link stakeholders' within and across different scales (Guerrero et al., 2013)

qualitative method I tried “to understand how everyday knowledge about the environment is formed” (Peters, 2017, p. 128).

I combined the three methodical components into a single interview schedule with three parts to optimize the data collection phase of this study. The study was conducted from August of 2023 to January of 2024, comprising a total of eight interviews.

Of the eight interviews,

- Six interviews were done in person in Derry~Londonderry (one completed online) and two conducted entirely online.
- Seven interviews were conducted with individual participants, while one involved two participants simultaneously.

All interviews were audio-recorded and subsequently transcribed using HappyScribe (Scribe, n.d.) transcription service (more information on this in *Section 4.6 Data Analysis*).

The interview questions were framed to elicit responses from participants in their capacity as representatives of their respective groups. Although one participant, lacking a formal Lough Foyle stakeholder affiliation, responded from a private perspective based on their personal connection to Lough Foyle from growing up in Lough Foyle area.

Prior to each interview, participants were informed of the voluntary nature of their participation, the anonymization of their personal information and the destruction of the audio recording after transcription. To ensure transparency, the beginning and end of the audio recordings were verbally announced during each interview. Interviews were designed to not exceed one hour in duration. In three instances, the network survey component was completed via email following the primary interview.

The participatory mapping part was integrated into the open-ended questions on activities of the group in Lough Foyle of the semi-structured interviews²³. Participants were requested to identify decisive ecological and natural features of Lough Foyle on a map. For the in-person interviews, a hard copy map enclosed in a washable cover was provided along with washable pens. Online interviewees received a Portable Document Format (PDF) version of the identical map. The interviewees were asked to delineate areas important to them by drawing on the map. All these drawings were from memory except for one online interview, where the map was sent via email post-interview.

The concluding segment of the interview protocol incorporated a network survey designed to assess inter-group collaboration and communication patterns. This survey utilized a hybrid approach combining roster and recall methodologies and thus mitigating the risk of omitting stakeholders (Makkonen et al., 2018). A predefined list of groups served as the foundation, with provisions for expansion based on participants’ suggestions of additional relevant groups. The survey aimed to

²³ The complete interview schedule can be found in the Appendix.

construct a weighted social network and identify key stakeholders within the Lough Foyle area. Connections between groups were categorized and weighted as follows:

- Communication: Defined as less frequent and less strong connections but involving knowledge exchange.
- Collaboration: Characterized by more frequent and strong connections, including joint project participation and fundraising.

A temporal element was also integrated into the network survey to evaluate the potential impact of temporal markers, such as Brexit, on inter-group connections.

The first part of the interview had a semi-structured format with open-ended questions. There was a total of 23 primary and follow-up questions which covered the following themes:

- Group categorization
- Group activities and interests in Lough Foyle
- Understandings of ecological or natural features within Lough Foyle
- Understandings of boundaries (both general and specific to Lough Foyle)
- Understandings of Temporal markers (explicitly Brexit, but not limited to it)
- Knowledge and understandings of transboundary projects and knowledge flows

This methodological approach was designed to understand in-depth stakeholders' perspectives on various aspects of Lough Foyle's social-ecological system.

Despite the limited sample size, this approach yielded a robust qualitative dataset, facilitating a comprehensive and in-depth analysis of stakeholder perspectives on the themes. The subsequent sections of this study focus on the analysis and discussion of the insights gleaned from these thematic areas, providing a nuanced understanding of stakeholders' views on and their implications for the management and governance of Lough Foyle. Specifically, the questions this thesis focuses on aim to (see Table 1 for the exact questions asked):

- Explore the stakeholders' understandings of Lough Foyle's boundaries and the potential mismatches these boundaries entail
- Explore how borders affect different connections between communities on either side

Table 1: Questions of the Interview schedule which fall under the main Theme of boundaries, with primary questions and potential follow questions²⁴ (Source: Author's own).

Primary Questions	Follow-up Questions
<p>What does your group perceive as a boundary?</p>	
<p>Are there any boundary or border issues?</p>	<p>Is it important for [group name] to have a border in this area?</p>
	<p>Could a (Marine) Protected Area be a solution to boundary issues?</p>
	<p>How would you imagine the activities to change, if there is a set border?</p>

²⁴ The complete interview schedule can be found in the Appendix.

Reflection box 4.4 Data Collection

As mentioned in *Reflection box 4.2 Field Work*, the choice of interview location is one aspect I would reconsider. Four of the eight interviews took place in cafés with significant background noise, which impacted both my concentration and the quality of the audio recordings.

Also, to ensure comparability of the interviews, I aimed to keep the time gap between the first and last interviews short. Conducting interviews over an extended period risks shifting the emphasis in the questioning process when insights accumulate from earlier discussions. This can potentially reduce the comparability of the interviews. Furthermore, as interviews progress, additional questions can emerge, making it challenging to ask these same questions to earlier participants. To mitigate this issue from the outset, we opted for a semi-structured interview format and asked participants if they would be open to follow-up questions after the interviews.

Additionally, while concentrating interview questions on one single place risks imbuing that place with greater significance than it may hold in everyday perceptions. My observation though suggests that Lough Foyle holds importance to all participants I interviewed²⁵. This resonates with Anderson's (2010) conceptualization of the "research encounter as polylogue", which reframes a dialogue – or interview - into a 'polylogue', which "includ[es] not simply the researcher [and] the researched, but also place" (Anderson et al., 2010, p. 598). Place here is not only the geographical location being researched but also "the place in which the methodology is being practiced" (Anderson et al., 2010, p. 598).

4.6 Data analysis

The qualitative data from this study includes the recorded interviews, visual recordings of the maps generated during the participatory mapping part, and the descriptions of these maps as captured in the interview recordings. The quantitative data consists of the participants' responses to the network survey.

The interviews were recorded and transcribed using artificial intelligence (AI) assisted transcription software, HappyScribe (Scribe, n.d.). The implementation of AI tools for interview transcription in this case study provided an efficient alternative to manual methods, significantly reducing time investment and researcher fatigue (Thippanna et al., 2023). While this automation offered considerable procedural advantages, it necessitated careful consideration of the reliability and accuracy of AI-generated transcripts (Siddique, 2024). Thus, I reviewed - and corrected if necessary - the initial AI assisted transcription to ensure their accuracy. While reviewing, I also took notes of my impressions. These transcribed interviews, along with my notes, serve as the primary data for the qualitative analysis. See Figure 6 for an excerpt of the transcripts²⁶.

²⁵ "The passion of everybody I talked to is evidence for the importance of Lough Foyle to the stakeholders" (quote from notes while reviewing the interview transcriptions)

²⁶ To protect participant anonymity, the complete transcripts are not included in the Appendix.

[00:31:13.060] - Interviewee

It's a space to watch. But actually what I believe is that these arrangements, like the North South institutional arrangements, are a protective factor against those things happening. Provided that legislators at the centre take account of issues where you've got a land border and a marine border. I mean, Brexit came out of the minds of people who had no idea, really, or no consciousness, really, that there was a land border between the UK and Ireland that was going to turn into an external EU border. I think a lot of the governance that's in place, for example, in the northwest and in the East border region, for Carlingford, as well, is protective against the disruption, the potential damage and disruption that Brexit has caused. But Brexit has done, more than anything else, has to an extent undone a lot of the trust between the different political blocks. It can make decision-making around cross-border issues difficult. But that's only if the decision-making is presented as an identity-related issue. So where environmental, agricultural, marine issues are concerned, if those things are seen as having merit in their own, having an intrinsic merit, then they don't become part of the identity argument, if you know what I mean.

[00:32:45.470] - Interviewee

The biggest risk that Brexit poses is the ignorance of a Westminster government about the particular conditions and circumstances that Northern Ireland has. The biggest risk of Brexit in terms of any external border is probably on animal and plant health issues in terms of that potential divergence and drifts I told you about. Yeah. So all of the governance infrastructure that's been in place here has lessened the shock, the potential shock caused by Brexit.

[00:33:22.200] - Jonas

Okay, thank you. Besides Brexit, are there any other temporal markers that would have changed management of the Foyle in the past? You said the 1998 agreement, are there any more?

[00:33:44.920] - Interviewee

I suppose not that I'm aware of, really. 1952 is a key point because that was the establishment of the Foyle and Carlingford lights commission. You can look at the legislation that gives the terms of operation and that's available online. 1952 and 1998 were key, really. The Lough's Agency, for example, also has the statutory responsibility for reporting on water frameworks directive now to the Irish government, but would have reported to both governments on water frameworks directive requirements as affecting the systems for which it had jurisdiction for Foyle and Carlingford. It continues to do that.

Figure 6: Excerpt of the transcripts generated by HappyScribe (Source: Authors own).

I analyzed the primary data by employing a coding process with the qualitative analysis software MAXQDA 2024 (VERBI Software, 2024). I used MAXQDA for data organization to organize the data and literature into projects, MAXQDA's term for thematic folders. For example, by creating a project called interview transcripts I could connect themes found within the individual interview with similar themes in other interviews and the reviewed literature. MAXQDA provided an integrated platform for both literature review and interview analysis. This enabled a coding process that facilitated meaningful connections between theoretical frameworks and empirical data which could be summarized into a report. This report gave me a thematic reference document which I could revisit throughout the analysis process when clarification was needed, instead of going through each document again.

4.6.1 Coding

Coding is a reiterative, layered and structured process of identifying themes to understand meanings in a text. Peters (2017, p. 178) notes that coding organizes the data by “highlighting and grouping information around topics crucial to our research question” and identifies thematic intersections between codes, which then can connect the empirical findings with broader literature. (Clifford et al., 2016; Peters, 2017)

For this coding process, I employed a combination of deductive and inductive approaches. A deductive approach uses predefined codes based on existing frameworks or themes, while an inductive approach allows themes to emerge directly from the data without predefined codes (Peters, 2017). Initially, I began with a deductive approach, where the selected codes were drawn from the main themes in the interview

schedule²⁷. This approach helped provide an overview of the common themes that linked the interviewees' responses.

Then, while analyzing the interviews, I adopted an inductive approach to supplement the deductive approach. Through this, new patterns and themes emerged from the data, and it enabled the discovery of unexpected insights, which may have been overlooked with a purely deductive approach (Peters, 2017). This inductive approach also helped to specify the research rationales of this work. This culminated in a merged approach to the analysis, with deductive and inductive elements. For example, in the first iteration of coding I deductively categorized the interview data into a 'boundary' theme, then inductively analyzed these categorized excerpts to develop the findings presented in *Chapter 5. Results and Discussion*. This exemplifies how the deductive approach guided the initial data organization while allowing inductive reasoning to inform the analytical outcomes²⁸.

4.6.2 Other data

The mapping exercise produced visual data, highlighting areas of importance to each individual interviewee. This data has not yet been analyzed and is not part of this thesis. For more details, see *Reflection box 4.5 Data Analysis*.

The network survey gave us weighted information on the connections between the groups, allowing us to establish a social network visually. These connections were implemented into the network analysis and visualization software *Gephi* (Bastian et al., 2009) for further analysis. While the analysis of the quantitative data was not pursued further in this thesis, the insights of the verbatim accounts gained from the inter-group connections were integrated into the qualitative analysis of the interviews. For more details, refer to *Reflection box 4.5 Data Analysis*.

Reflection box 4.5 Data Analysis

This thesis focuses on qualitative data derived from semi-structured interviews rather than statistical inference. While additional data was collected (see *Section 4.6.2 Other data*), their analysis is not part of this thesis. The sample size (eight participant interviews from a stakeholder pool of 47 groups, with only five participants completing the social network survey) does not constitute a statistically significant dataset.

Additionally, the extent of this analysis is constrained by the parameters of my master's thesis. While three datasets were collected (the interviews, participatory mapping, and social network survey), incorporating all would exceed the appropriate dimensions of this master's thesis. Therefore, my analysis focuses specifically on the qualitative data and only on one theme of the open-ended interview questions, which provided the most robust dataset of the three methods employed.

²⁷ The main themes can be found in the complete interview schedule in the Appendix.

²⁸ A detailed list of the codesystem used in the analysis of the interview transcripts can be found in the Appendix. The specific codes from the interviews transcripts have been omitted to ensure participant anonymity.

To appropriately engage with the rationales underpinning this thesis, the interviews were analyzed using a qualitative approach, which allowed for an in-depth exploration of participants' perspectives and the contextual nuances of the *Lough Foyle Space*. This critical examination of the interviews goes beyond describing the data and interrogates the underlying social and political forces shaping it. Qualitative data can lead to partial understandings and multiple complex responses that cannot be easily generalized and therefore give nuance. This provides rich insights into human experiences and perspectives that cannot be captured through quantitative data alone (Peters, 2017).

Also, to maintain transparency and accountability, and to honor participants' time and their contributions, my research collaborator and I will explore potential applications for the data not analyzed within this thesis. This may include outreach material, providing feedback for the participant, and producing research reports that incorporate all data collected from this study.

4.7 Participant feedback

During the planning stage, and while providing participants with updates on the progress of our work, I envisioned what I termed a 'retribution event' (for reflections on the negative connotation of this term, please see *Reflection box 4.6 'Retribution Event'* below). For this event I would travel to Derry~Londonderry to give in-person feedback to participants, either in one-on-one events to ensure their anonymity or, if agreed upon, in small group settings. To facilitate this, I amended our ethics approval to cover these feedback events²⁹.

To ensure the anonymity of the participants during these events we considered presenting our results in a generalized manner. However, this would have posed a challenge given that Lough Foyle is a relatively small community and even when presenting results anonymously and in a generalized form, it was likely that attendees would still be able to identify other participants based on the context of the findings.

I aimed to hold these events for two key reasons. First, to provide feedback to the participants, allowing them to see how I had used the data they shared with me. And secondly, to gather their feedback on my interpretation of the data, ensuring that I accurately understood their input. If my understanding differs from what is trying to be conveyed, this might lead to significantly different interpretations of the data. By doing so I also aimed to ensure transparency, data sovereignty and the intellectual property of the participants as outlined in *Section 4.2 Ethics*.

Personal commitments prevented me from traveling to Derry~Londonderry during the timeframe I had originally envisioned for these events. Given the time constraints of this master's thesis, I decided to cancel the in-person feedback events. This was communicated to the participants, who were then asked if they still wished to receive feedback, and if so, in what format. I offered them three options while also encouraging them to suggest alternative methods for receiving feedback.

The three options were:

²⁹ The ethics approval of the Commission for Research Impact Assessment and Ethics of the University of Oldenburg can be found in the Appendix.

1. A written report with the option of answering questions via email
2. An online presentation and discussion
3. A combination of the above, a written report and an online meeting afterwards

The participants expressed a preference for options 1 and 3, indicating that they were all interested in receiving feedback, with some also showing interest in this thesis.

Reflection box 4.6 'Retribution Event'

The term, 'retribution event' requires critical examination in this context. When asked Perplexity, a generative artificial intelligence, "What is a retribution event in context of stakeholder feedback?" the answer was:

"In the context of stakeholder feedback, a retribution event refers to a situation where stakeholders face negative consequences or reprisals for providing feedback, especially critical or negative feedback" (*Perplexity*, n.d.),

and the Cambridge online dictionary defines retribution as: "deserved and severe punishment" (*Cambridge.org*, 2024).

This terminology, used without further reflection, does not align with the principles of respectful stakeholder engagement that guided my research (see *Section 4.2 Ethics*). In the future I will avoid this term, because of its immediate negative connotation and intimidating nature.

4.8 Conclusion

This chapter has outlined the methodological framework guiding this research, including the rationale for site selection, stakeholder identification processes, and the methodological approach to data collection and analysis employed in this case study. Emphasis in this chapter lies on *Section 4.2 Ethics*, as it highlights the general ethical considerations when researching (humans) and the ethical reflections that guided this project and this case study specifically.

Concluding this chapter, the thesis has established the foundational framework through an exposition of the key rationales, relevant literature, and methodological approaches. The preceding three chapters serve to inform the subsequent *Chapter 5. Results and Discussion*. Herein I analyze the interviews through the theoretical lenses articulated in *Chapter 3. Literature Review*, using the methodology detailed in this chapter, all while maintaining focus on the two key rationales established in *Chapter 2. Introduction*. Namely, that resolving existing spatial mismatches in the *Lough Foyle Space* would require a formal 'agreement' between the Republic of Ireland and the United Kingdom on the precise location of the border and, that borders constrain connections between communities on either side.

5 Results and Discussion

This chapter discusses the participants' understandings of boundaries as shared during the interviews. This helps me to respond to the research rationales established in *Chapter 2. Introduction*. Specifically, that resolving existing spatial mismatches in the *Lough Foyle Space* requires a formal 'agreement' between the Republic of Ireland (ROI) and the United Kingdom (UK) on the precise location of the border. And that borders constrain various connections across them. This analysis builds upon the theoretical framework developed in *Chapter 3. Literature Review*, while employing the methodological approaches detailed in *Chapter 4. Methods*.

So, beginning with *Section 5.2 Multilevel constructions and mismatches in Lough Foyle Space* I analyze the multilevel construction of *Lough Foyle Space* (for a definition of this concept see *Chapter 2. Introduction*) and how this construction leads to *spatial mismatches*. Specifically, the status quo of a missing formal 'agreement' on the precise location of a border in Lough Foyle leads to a lack of aquaculture licensing process that creates a multilevel *spatial mismatch*, where political and administrative spaces do not align with neither functional space nor environmental space.

In *Section 5.3 Borders without boundaries: Pragmatism and the border*, this thesis highlights two key *spatial mismatches* in *Lough Foyle Space*. The first is a *spatial mismatch* between official policy frameworks and lived realities, where the construction of nation states and their borders creates misaligned spaces. The second is a *spatial mismatch* between the understanding-of the border in everyday life and its 'reality' on a map.

In sections *5.4 Borders, Disruptors* and *5.6 Borders, Spaces of connection* this thesis explores different aspects of borders in the *Lough Foyle Space*. While borders can disrupt various flows and relationships, they also serve as spaces of connection and collaboration. Although borders can significantly influence human flows and relationships, more-than-human entities are either minimally affected or remain unaffected altogether.

This is further explored in *Section 5.5 'Wet Borders'*, where the fluid materiality of Lough Foyle challenges the rigid territoriality of nation states. By adopting a 'wet ontology' - an approach that lends from water's character as liquid, mobile and dynamic (see Steinberg & Peters, 2015) - I show that in the *Lough Foyle Space* borders do not constrain various connections across them as initially assumed by the research team.

In *Section 5.7 'Useful' boundaries*, this thesis proposes for managing purposes, that replacing the concept of national borders with ecosystem boundaries may be useful to better manage the social-ecological system (SES) of Lough Foyle. It is also argued that managing a cross-border ecosystem requires careful consideration of the various scales and levels at which an ecosystem exists. This entails rethinking traditional approaches and overcoming ontological boundaries to develop innovative strategies for transboundary management.

5.1 Introduction

At the outset of this project, the research team's investigation sought to examine whether the absence of a defined, official state border in marine management contexts would generate *spatial mismatches* in *Lough Foyle Space*³⁰. To alleviate such mismatches, it would require an 'agreement' on the exact location of the border, in this case United Kingdom and Republic of Ireland in Lough Foyle. Alongside mismatches, we were also seeking to understand whether borders constrain connections between communities or facilitate them in the SES that is *Lough Foyle Space*. To explore these lines of enquiry, the participants selected (see *Chapter 4. Methods*) were asked whether they believed it would be important for the Republic of Ireland and the United Kingdom (UK) to reach an 'agreement' on the exact location of the border that separates the two States (see Table 1). This was carried out in a careful and mindful manner, considering the political and historical context of the research area (see *Chapter 4. Methods*).

Moreover, it is crucial here to distinguish between *borders* and *boundaries*, as the participants often used these terms interchangeably. Additionally, in much of the literature, the term *border* is frequently used synonymously with *boundary* (Turner, 2016). This differs from how this thesis defines these concepts and distinguishes between them in this work. For clarity, this thesis adopts Reece Jones' definition of the distinction between borders and boundaries³¹, which is as follows:

"I prefer boundary to be a broad term that refers to any type of division whether it is a semantic divider between categories or a line-on-the-ground political division. I reserve the term border specifically for the latter case of territorialized line-on-the-ground political borders" (Jones, 2009, p. 180).

Additionally, it is essential to differentiate between *scale* and *level* and to define *space* in this context. This thesis adopts Gibson et al.'s (2000) definition of scale as the "spatial, temporal, quantitative, or analytical dimensions used to measure and study any phenomenon" (p. 218). In contrast, *level* refers to specific points along a scale. However, in the literature, the term *level* is often found as *scale*, contrary to the distinction maintained here (Borges et al., 2020).

Furthermore, in this context, and drawing inspiration from Peters (2017), *space* encompasses Euclidian and non-Euclidian dimensions and *space* can span several different scales and levels. *Space* here is constructed through the "relations that form it" (Peters, 2017, p. 33). So, *space* operates across multiple dimensions, with the following two dimensions emerging as the most salient in this analysis: the dimension of Euclidian area and the dimension of human understanding.

The definition of *space* applies to the dimensions of *spatial mismatches* as well. Drawing upon Guerrero et al.'s (2013) conceptualization of scale mismatches - defined as occurring "when conservation actions are undertaken at a scale that does not reflect the scale(s) required to solve a target conservation problem"

³⁰ Further discussion on *Space* and *spatial mismatches* is provided below.

³¹ In the following quotes, I retain the verbatim account while using brackets to clarify when participants' views differ from my perspective and Jones' distinctions.

(p. 36) – this study adopts a broader definition of *spatial mismatches* referring to instances where two or more spatial dimensions do not, or do not fully overlap (also see **Figure 2** in *Chapter 3. Literature Review* for illustration). Included in this definition is, for example, that discrepancies between spatial dimensions of understanding and the ‘reality’ on a map can create *spatial mismatch(es)*. See the following Sections *5.2 Multilevel constructions and mismatches in Lough Foyle Space* and *5.3 Borders without boundaries: Pragmatism and the border* for further discussions on *spatial mismatches* in *Lough Foyle Space*.

5.2 Multilevel constructions and mismatches in *Lough Foyle Space*

Building on this understanding of space as both Euclidian and non-Euclidian, provides a foundation to see how these spatial dimensions play out concretely in the context of Lough Foyle, offering insight into how *spatial mismatches* emerge. In *Lough Foyle Space* a key point to consider is that borders (and nation states) generally necessitate an understanding of a multilevel construction, wherein *space* is transformed into territory through processes enacted by various actors, not only nation states (Laine, 2016). Such spaces can be utilized by these actors for multiple purposes across different temporal and spatial levels (Sternlieb et al., 2013). This multilevel and multi-purpose construction frequently results in mismatches between the national level and scales of identity, organization, and lived experience (Laine, 2016). Laine (2016) also highlights the concept of organizational scale as it manifests across functional, environmental, political and administrative spaces. Functional spaces do not always coincide with political or administrative or environmental spaces (Haselsberger, 2014), which can lead to multiple *spatial mismatches*.

In the context of Lough Foyle, the political and administrative alignment process regarding the contested tenure of the foreshore, and the resulting status quo of a non-existent aquaculture licensing process, has led to multilevel *spatial mismatch* (see *Section 4.3.1 Description of research site* and **Table 2**). Specifically, there is neither an overlap between the political and administrative spaces, and the functional space (as everyday actions and mobility on and around Lough Foyle remain unaffected). Nor is there overlap between the political and administrative spaces and the environmental space, where Pacific Oyster aquaculture practices continue. As evidenced by a participant who gives us insights into the mismatch between the political and administrative spaces and the functional space:

“I always use the example that if you looked at the car park for one of the main employers in the town, Seagate, just on the edge of the city, there's around half of the car park with Donegal registrations. So, the employees that income is benefiting Donegal. But you could say the same about employers in Letterkenny, where a lot of the cars would be Northern Ireland registered vehicles. So again, the economy's in a circular environment in that those are key structures for us” (Interview 1, August 2023).

And a mismatch in the environmental space:

“I mean, the original time we noticed the trestles, it was from a map. It wasn't because anybody had reported having the first set of trestles there. Now they're very, very apparent

on any imagery that you look at. Any Google image you'll see them, there's lots of them."

(Interview 7, December 2023)

Furthermore, the multilevel mismatch represents what Chilla et al., (2012) identify as the "most important barrier." The nation-state functions as a multilevel construction in which the nation-state itself is "constantly negotiated and reconfigured by its actors at different levels" (Laine, 2016, p. 467). In *Lough Foyle Space*, this complexity manifests through misaligned administrative and political jurisdictions across borders (see Table 2). Land tenure is claimed on the national level and as private property in the United Kingdom's case, as the Crown Estate claims ownership of all the seabed out to UK's exclusive economic zone. While management operates on a different level despite national oversight. Local activities often proceed independently of these other levels (Ansong, 2021). Table 2 maps key institutional stakeholders and their interests in Lough Foyle, illustrating the overlapping governmental remits and multiple land tenure claims. This mapping exemplifies the ease with which *spatial mismatches* can arise within the *Lough Foyle Space*.

Table 2: Key institutional stakeholders, their remits and spatial claims (Interests) in Lough Foyle Space (Source: Hughes, 2021).

Stakeholder	Jurisdiction	Interest
Loughs Agency/FCILC/NSMC	UK & Rol	Responsible for Lough Foyle fisheries management
Foreign and Commonwealth Office	UK	Claims Lough Foyle as territory
The Crown Estate	UK	Claims Lough Foyle as property
Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade (DFAT)	Rol	Claims Lough Foyle as territory
Department of Agriculture, Environment and Rural Affairs (DAERA)	UK	Sponsors Loughs Agency/FCILC Responsible for fisheries-related issues
Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications (DECC)	Rol	Sponsors Loughs Agency/FCILC
Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM)	Rol	Responsible for seafood and aquaculture
Food Standards Agency (FSA)	UK	Inspects shellfish food safety
Food Safety Authority Ireland (FSAI)	Rol	Responsible for overseeing food safety
Sea Fisheries Protection Agency (SFPA)	Rol	Responsible for conserving fisheries Licenses and inspects seafood on behalf of FSAI

5.3 Borders without boundaries: Pragmatism and the border

An analysis of participant responses to the question regarding the importance of the exact location of the border, revealed that the majority (5) indicated no perceived importance regarding the establishment of a defined border in Lough Foyle, while the remaining participants (3) expressed indifference to the potential location of such a border, should one be established. The exact question asked was: Is it important for your group to have a border in this area? These stakeholder groups demonstrated what might be revealed as a pragmatic approach, acknowledging their limited agency in border determination processes.

As articulated by one participant:

“There are political boundaries [borders], but we'd stay away from those. It's counterproductive for us to get into a political debate” (Interview 1, August 2023).

And another participant adds, when asked about the necessity of the exact location of the border:

“In terms of legislation, in terms of management, in terms of policy, that's the border we have to work on and that's the border that [our] work would fall in” (Interview 4, August 2023).

And:

“The border is there and it's a bit beyond our control” (Interview 4, August 2023).

These quotes illustrate that while the political border may indeed represent a mismatch, it is something *within which* participants must work. This perspective is further corroborated by another participant, who emphasized that despite the contested political border, it exists *outside* their sphere of immediate concern and demonstrates no measurable impact to everyday activities. They stated:

“Both claim it, but they don't really fall out about it. What would you say? Sort of pushed. It's not mentioned. And they all get on and everybody does their own thing” (Interview 2, August 2023).

So, while the participants acknowledge the disputed border, the current indeterminate status, and any potential future resolution, has and would have negligible impact on their everyday activities,

“[...] unless it precipitated a change in the status quo with the aquaculture licensing. Then I suppose they would see that as a positive to try and push forward the aquaculture licensing and get that in place” (Interview 6, September 2023).

This was articulated by a participant regarding potential changes to Pacific Oyster aquaculture regulations under a defined border. By this, the interviewee means that even if an ‘agreement’ were reached on the exact location of the border in Lough Foyle, the joint legislation on aquaculture (see *Section 4.3.2 History*) would still need to be enacted; the mere establishment of a border would have minimal impact on Pacific Oyster aquaculture activities. Until then, the participants have adapted pragmatically to the current border situation, though they acknowledge that the undefined status does make their work *“really, really difficult”*, (Interview 4, August 2023), as a participant stated, in terms of navigating the fragmented management of Lough Foyle.

Moreover, the evident limitations in these stakeholder groups' capacity to influence border determination indicate a significant disconnect between official policy frameworks and lived realities, or what we might think of as a *spatial mismatch* as per definition in this work (see *Section 5.1 Introduction*). This is crystalized into the statement:

“[D]iplomacy is at work and we'll have to leave it to them to sort out” (Interview 1, August 2023).

By this, the interviewee means that while Lough Foyle is contested by both Northern Ireland (NI) and ROI, “*the environment doesn't change just because of a political boundary*” (Interview 1, August 2023), and the participant sees a

“[...] pressing need for a policy context that both jurisdictions can buy into, [...] to ensure the integrity of the system [...] as a shared place between all the communities that face onto the Foyle” (Interview 1, August 2023).

This perspective highlights how, despite the political contestation between Northern Ireland and the Republic of Ireland over Lough Foyle, the environmental and social realities of the area remain constant. Furthermore, analysis of the interview data also reveals an additional mismatch – one between participants’ everyday experience, where the land border in the *Lough Foyle Space* is largely imperceptible in daily life contrary to its cartographic representation as a definitive border. This thesis calls this a *spatial mismatch* in the dimension of human perception or a *mismatch in understanding*.

While reflecting on boundaries in the *Lough Foyle Space*, a participant stated that

“[t]he easy one is the jurisdictional boundary [border]. That's the geopolitical reality” (Interview 1, August 2023).

This reflects a pragmatic acceptance of borders as fixed realities around which daily life must be negotiated. Newman (2006) characterizes this phenomenon as an “interesting border curiosity” (p.153), where residents demonstrate a stoic acknowledgment of border constraints while pursuing their everyday activities unimpeded by the border.

As Newman further writes,

“[c]itizens of the Republic [ROI] will make the short five-minute trek over the (non-existent) border each evening so that they can drink in a pub where smoking is still allowed (until, that is, the UK introduces its own laws to ban smoking in restaurants and pubs serving food). When, because of the drinking laws in the UK, the pubs in the north call out their last orders, citizens of the north can always make their own five-minute sojourn over the (non-existent) boundary [border] to continue drinking in the (smokeless) pubs and bars of the south” (Newman, 2006, p. 153).

Returning to *Lough Foyle Space*, another participant responded the following to the question: What does your group perceive as a boundary?

“We don't generally recognize any boundaries [borders] because [...] fish don't recognize Lough Foyle and its... Any boundaries [including borders], real or otherwise” (Interview 6, September 2023).

This response highlights the understanding of the border in the *Lough Foyle Space*³², paralleling Husár et al.'s (2018) observations of border perception in post-Schengen Europe. The situation exemplifies a mismatch in understanding between lived experience and the border's symbolic significance (Husár et al., 2018), reflecting broader patterns in how border communities *perceive, experience, narrate* and *negotiate* borders in their everyday realities (Español et al., 2021).

This situation exemplifies a de-bordering process, where everyday activities proceed largely unaffected by borders. While bordering processes carry political implications, they ultimately depend on the daily practices and performances of local residents to become 'real' (Pöttsch, 2018). The border's significance (or lack thereof) emerges through residents' choices to either generate or disregard social and personal divisions in their everyday lives (Español et al., 2021).

Nevertheless, bordering as a social construct impacts border communities through the state's deployment of "concrete, economic and coercive power[s]" (O'Dowd, 2010 in Pöttsch, 2018). This process can disrupt social cohesion and thereby reinforce the constructed lines and compartments that form the world we live in (Newman, 2006).

The disruptive element of borders is examined in greater depth in the next section.

5.4 Borders, Disruptors

This section delves into the disruptive elements inherent in border spaces and analyses their particular implications for the *Lough Foyle Space*. This section starts with a quote from a participant in which the notion of non-perception of borders is corroborated, while adding an additional aspect – disruption – to the understanding of borders.

"We don't perceive boundaries [borders]. We work across them. We deal with whatever is drawn on the map, but we try to minimize the impact of that in terms of environmental sustain, building people's capacity to work in a way in which borders are the least disruption is caused by administration of borders as possible. [...] [I]n a sense, the paradigm that we work on is different" (Interview 3, August 2023).

They add:

"I guess the border has to go somewhere. Setting a border in the Foyle as to where it is, is not going to solve anything" (Interview 3, August 2023).

Another participant puts it this way:

"It's not necessarily about seabed ownership or defining a maritime boundary [border] for us, it's very much about coming to a framework agreement on the use of the seabed without the need to define the owner, if you know what I mean, without the need to

³² Although, Andersen (2024) comes to an opposing conclusion in their study on border temporalities in Derry~Londonderry. See *Section 3.4 Lough Foyle* for more details.

define a maritime boundary [border], an official maritime boundary [border]" (Interview 6, September 2023).

These participants understand the border as both a potential and actual disruptor to the “mobility of people, goods and ideas” (Husár et al., 2018, p. 132), with demonstrable impacts on aquaculture licensing. Such disruption poses tangible threats to both environmental integrity and landscape aesthetics, as is the case of Pacific Oyster aquafarming. This concern carries particular significance for (marine) tourism in Ireland's Northwest, as noted by a government stakeholder, when talking about cross-border tourism in the *Lough Foyle Space*:

“[Cross-border tourism is] linked up between the Wild Atlantic Way and the Causeway Coast and those types of things. That's essential now given that visitor experience has to have that flow across the border. It can't just stop” (Interview 6, September 2023).

Although the disruptive impact of the border in this area is already lessened, as a participant explained:

“The region suffered because of the enforcement of borders, but in itself, because of family connections and everything, there was always this community cohesion across the border” (Interview 3, August 2023).

In this case border means the set and defined static land border. The participant added that:

“In Ireland, Northern Ireland, there's quite a long capacity and awareness in the two systems of the need to lessen the disruption of borders and boundaries on things like the economy, on trade, on logistics and stuff. That actually predates the peace process. That was in both systems for a long time, quite simply because people saw the rationale for it” (Interview 3, August 2023).

This rationale turns a border dispute into a practical transactional negotiation. Or in the words of a participant:

“For us, it's not so much a maritime boundary [border] dispute as it is... Simply, we need a resolution to where payments are made and who payments are made to” (Interview 6, September 2023).

When border regions are treated as peripheral areas in (marine) spatial planning (Bertram, 2024), borders can become obstacles that disrupt natural, cultural, social, economic, and functional flows and relationships within cross-border regions (Haselsberger, 2014; Hippe, 2024; Husár et al., 2018; Taubenböck et al., 2023). This dynamic gives rise to a "plurality of disruptions" (Laine, 2021). While these disruptions may not uniformly affect all aspects of cross-border interactions to the same extent, the tension between facilitating cross-border cooperation and addressing prevention and security concerns in bordering processes can exacerbate the negative impacts on environmental and functional spaces (Haselsberger, 2014).

Anecdotally, my personal experiences of crossing this international border differs from the dynamics described in the preceding paragraph. For an anecdotal account of this cross-border experience, see *Reflection Box 5.1 A Border Experience* below. My observations align with the "interesting border curiosity" described by Newman (2006) in the previous section. I further draw on this experience to reinforce the argument presented in *Section 5.5 Borders, Spaces of connection*, where this thesis discusses borders not only as lines of division and disruption but also as spaces of connection.

Before delving into that discussion, an additional dimension of borders observed in the *Lough Foyle Space* is explored. The following section focuses on how borders influence and are influenced by more-than-human entities.

Reflection Box 5.1 A Border Experience

For the field work conducted in this case study, I arranged an accommodation in Derry~Londonderry. The most convenient travel route from Germany was to fly into Dublin and take a bus directly from the airport to Derry~Londonderry. During the journey, I only realized we had crossed the border into Northern Ireland when the road signs switched from kilometres to miles, and Derry~Londonderry was referred to as Londonderry rather than Derry. There were no border checks or checkpoints—a stark contrast to my experiences growing up and living in southwestern Germany, where I frequently crossed the French-German border via disused checkpoints that no longer enforced border controls.

This experience felt new to me for two reasons. First, unlike the French-German border, with the border checkpoint I was familiar with, I could only situate myself here when reading the signs, as there were no border checkpoints. Second, it contradicted my expectations shaped by UK's departure from the European Union (EU), where I had anticipated more pronounced border formalities.

5.5 ‘Wet Borders’

Borders, as discussed in the previous section, can act as disruptors to human mobility, the flow of ideas, and the movement of goods. So, “[...] human activity within these boundaries can be policed, nonhuman actants may show no similar respect” (Bear, 2013, p. 28), such as oyster larvae. Pacific oyster larvae, for instance, drift with ocean currents during their planktonic stage, effectively becoming part of the ocean's dynamic system (Child et al., 1995). As a result, while a nation's laws govern its territorial waters, they do not extend to the ocean beyond its jurisdiction. Nor can such political jurisdictions manage ecological movements within and across space. Consequently, these larvae can reach a nation's shores from areas outside the scope of this nation's law enforcement.

Previous academic work has explored similar phenomenon where certain activities/materialities may pose border challenges, where they do not ‘respect’ such borders, by their very nature. For example, Peters has explored the offshore 'pirate' radio station, *Radio Caroline*, whereby electromagnetic waves failed to respect national borders (and laws) enabling broadcasters to circumvent UK broadcasting restrictions by operating from international waters. By transmitting powerful medium-wave frequencies,

the station reached millions of potential listeners within the UK, operating beyond the reach of domestic regulations (Peters, 2012).

Returning to *Lough Foyle Space*, a participant explained:

"Though we would often say our seas don't have boundaries [borders] even outside this Lough or if you go to the other side of Carlingford Lough, species and habitats, not so much habitats, but species will be highly migratory, they'll be mobile" (Interview 4, August 2023).

The participant described how static lines on a map, used to demarcate states, are inapplicable in this environmental context due to the fluid and dynamic nature of the environment itself. As Peters (2020) succinctly notes, "[t]he sea [...] is geophysically liquid, mobile, three-dimensional. You can draw a line on [a] map, but not the ocean itself. You can attempt to designate a zone, but the sea and life at sea move" (p.6). Only when leaving this fluidity behind and metaphorically 'setting foot onto land' does the concept of static border lines become applicable - and even then, only tenuously. The fluid nature of Lough Foyle continually challenges the constructed solidity of state borders. Lough Foyle's materiality, steady tidal movements and what Steinberg and Peters (2015) describe as "continual reformation" (p. 248) grant the lough its own agency, constructing its own spatiality beyond any (terrestrial) functions humans intend for it (Kanesu, 2024; Steinberg & Peters, 2015).

So, when a participant states that,

"[t]o be honest I don't think much would change if there was a set maritime boundary [border]. Again, I'm thinking from our perspective and the stakeholders that we have out there, like the fishermen themselves, anybody that's licensed with a vessel already are coming up against the boundary [border] effectively, jurisdictional boundary [border] for them is terrestrial. Once they land their catch, and if the catch has landed in Donegal, obviously, it's the Irish authorities and Irish legislation. If they land their catch in a Northern Ireland port like Lisahally Port, that's UK legislation and UK authorities" (Interview 6, September 2023).

It becomes evident that, while the catch can be landed in either UK or ROI territory - thus within a supposedly 'static zone,' as Steinberg (2011) describes - it is irrelevant where the catch was actually caught. As the participant suggests, imposing a fixed border or 'static zone' on the ocean fails to account for its inherent fluidity. The ocean's volume is constantly in motion, meaning "its territory and its location cannot be pinned down" (Steinberg & Peters, 2015, p. 254). To fully grasp this concept, we must adopt what Steinberg and Peters (2015) term 'wet ontologies', which emphasize the dynamic and ever-changing nature of oceanic spaces.

Thus, the concept of borders as 'static zones' is dismissed, rendering this notion irrelevant to Lough Foyle. But what happens once the 'catch is landed'? From a border studies perspective, the *Lough Foyle Space* can be conceptualized as a border space or as if existing in the 'middle of the Venn diagram'

(see Figure 7). Viewing it this way challenges the assumption of 'static zones' through a different lens, this time in a 'landed' context.

Being in the middle of a Venn diagram refers to occupying the overlapping elements of two or more systems. Such spaces enable “continuities, flows, and contacts” (Laine, 2021, p. 189) that transcend borders, providing opportunities to share knowledge and foster common areas of development (Durand, 2021).

Figure 7: Schematic illustration of the complex institutional interplay of funding, planning/management, and land tenure in the Lough Foyle Space. Institutional stakeholders interact at different jurisdictional levels. ¹UK Government, Scottish Government, Northern Ireland Executive, Welsh Government, Isle of Man Government, Government of Jersey, Government of Guernsey (Source: modified from Twomey 2020).

A participant describes this in more detail for *Lough Foyle Space*:

"There's more of an acceptance of the fluidity of the border here, but people integrate it into the template with which they view the world as opposed to it being a binary thing where you're constantly having, sort of, thinking about two systems that run in parallel. It's definitely a much more interwoven concept where you're standing in the middle of the Venn diagram as opposed to trying to solve it from one side or the other" (Interview 3, August 2023).

My experience as a European Union citizen³³ corroborates this notion of 'being on the inside' rather than encountering a definitive border. Despite crossing what technically constitutes an international border, my movement through this space revealed no traditional markers of border crossing. I conducted financial transactions seamlessly using standard payment methods, and notably, never encountered passport controls during my field work. This fluidity contrasted markedly with other international borders I have crossed (see *Reflection Box 5.1 A Border Experience*), requiring significantly less logistical preparation and administrative navigation.

The participant's account, alongside my experiences, reveals that *Lough Foyle Space* defies traditional conceptualizations of borders as fixed demarcation lines or 'static zones'. On the contrary, rather than marking an abrupt transition between distinct territories, here, as in any other border space, the social space is *negotiated, created and organized* by its inhabitants and a subsequent relational thinking of this space emerges, constituting a 'sense of place' that transcends rigid territorial division (Scott, 2021).

This correlates with the emergence of the *Northwest City Region, which can be seen* as 'in the middle of the Venn diagram'. A participant stated:

“But it has consistently grown into this Northwest City Region context where it's more about the place, that spatial entity, that catchment, and the people within it” (Interview 1, August 2023).

The *Northwest City Region* is a “tagline” (Interview 1, August 2023) the adjoining county councils (Donegal and Londonderry) have given the “shared space” (Interview 1, August 2023) - *Lough Foyle Space* – “because between Derry and Donegal we have about 350,000 people” (Interview 1, August 2023). So, the stakeholders' understanding of the *Lough Foyle Space* exemplifies Scott's (2020) concept of inclusive space-society relations. This mirrors the European integration process, facilitating what Jakubowski et al. (2022) describe as "political, societal, and economic territorial reorganization" (p. 2433), transforming the *Lough Foyle Space* into a space of contact and interaction.

Thus, the interview findings challenge initial research assumptions about border importance in the *Lough Foyle Space* (see research rationales in *Chapter 2. Introduction*).

This space exhibits dynamic, relational, and multidimensional characteristics that foster alternative political subjectivities and agencies (Brambilla & Jones, 2020; Jakubowski et al., 2022). This re-conceptualization enables novel approaches to land tenure when applying 'wet ontologies' to 'landed areas', creating what Brambilla and Jones, (2020) term "new conditions of possibility for agency" (p. 293).

This transformation emerged through a fundamental shift: viewing borders as spaces of connection rather than lines of division.

³³This is stated to show that in some respects I can do the same as a person with a ROI or UK passport.

5.6 Borders, Spaces of connection

Gerst et al. (2018) emphasize the inherent complexity of borders. As discussed in *Section 5.4 Borders, Disruptors*, borders can be an element to demarcate or delineate two or more spaces and they can disrupt the flow of goods and ideas, and the mobility of people. Despite their divisive aspects, borders also have connecting aspects. They function as 'gateways' (Durchlasspunkte) in their static enforcement aspect (Gerst et al., 2018) and operate as "engines of connectivity" (Durand, 2021, p. 311). This connectivity manifests through integration initiatives, social negotiation processes (Sohn, 2014; Wille, 2024) and everyday cultural experiences, exemplified by crossing the Polish-German border as a tourism appeal (Rogowski & Frąckowiak, 2023).

This is apparent in the *Lough Foyle Space*, which one participant described as a

"[...] cross-border functional economic area [...]" (Interview 3, August 2023),

in which

"[...] there was always this community cohesion across the border" (Interview 3, August 2023).

The historical context of Lough Foyle reveals an enduring conception of *"one region"* (Interview 3, August 2023) that transcends the formal border. The *Lough Foyle Space* inhabitants demonstrate what Rogowski and Frąckowiak (2023) identify as a shared borderland identity. This facilitates the emergence of a meaningful cross-border and *"one region"* (Interview 3, August 2023) mentality (Ritchie et al., 2020). Notably, this space maintains its permeability for daily mobility despite broader geopolitical shifts, in this case a 'hard Brexit'.

One participant stated:

"People just went to Donegal for their holidays and people from Donegal worked in Derry and that was what we did. I think what you have here is that sense of connectedness that wasn't disrupted as much by the border, where maybe in other parts of the border region for topographical reasons and because things happened like roads were closed and bridges were blown up for security reasons and movements were very limited, what you had in this region was the Foyle, which was this visible reminder that we are all one region" (Interview 3, August 2023).

Lough Foyle gives a "sense of connectedness". As a visible connector to the surrounding communities, it transforms this border space into what Wille (2024) describes with the term "spaces of possibility" (p. 97). This empowers local citizens with the agency to realize the *"one region"* (Interview 3, August 2023) vision, overcoming the lough's physical boundary.

Moreover, Lough Foyle,

"[...] had seamless cross-border cooperation where the land border didn't. That in itself also, I think, has an effect on the degree to which people understand and perceive the

border here because, yes, we had this security-related and customs border, but then we also had this sense that the Foyle belonged to everybody" (Interview 3, August 2023).

A participant stated that, despite Lough Foyle

"[...] represent[ing] a boundary between Northern Ireland and the Republic of Ireland in terms of its communities to a certain extent because there's a physical boundary there, a water boundary" (Interview 6, September 2023),

this boundary

"[...] has to be breached to have free flow of people. I suppose you've got the Foyle Ferry there that allows some interconnectedness across the Lough" (Interview 6, September 2023).

Through active negotiation processes, like establishing a ferry service at the mouth of Lough Foyle, the border undergoes constant reconstruction and maintenance - analogous to tidal movements - serving as a framework for social and political action (Laine, 2021). This process enables the border to be "breached" and the "interconnectedness" manifested into a "shared place" where borders minimally impact daily life.

Then, what are the fundamentals for such a transformation to occur?

A participant states that there should be a priority to

"[...] guide decision making [and] to ensure the integrity of the system itself as a water body, as a navigable channel, as an ecological complex, as a shared place between all the communities that face onto the Foyle" (Interview 1, August 2023).

This quote introduces an emotional and temporal dimension to the *Lough Foyle Space*, facilitating the aforementioned transformation by emphasizing the 'sense of place', which encompasses a shared communal history. It can also be interpreted as a call for a temporally and spatially integrated, as well as a functionally holistic management approach to the *Lough Foyle Space* - in the present, for the future, but also for the past, in form of shared communal memories (Laine, 2021).

This raises the question of how can Lough Foyle be managed in such an integrated and holistic manner? Or how can we reach a point where such management is possible? This thesis argues in the following passage that this can be achieved through cross-border collaboration.

Section 5.5 'Wet Borders' illustrates that borders in the *Lough Foyle Space* are less important than initially assumed by the research team and are not as disruptive as borders often can be. This prompts the question: Why is this the case? The section on the disruptive aspects of borders offers a clue, particularly in highlighting the "awareness [...] of the need to lessen the disruption of borders and boundaries" (Interview 3, August 2023). This awareness can also be described as cross-border collaboration.

Thus, revisiting the question of whether a set border is necessary, the responses extend beyond the issue of a mere identification of *spatial mismatch*, revealing deeper insights into the value of cross-border cooperation.

Two participants from different stakeholder groups stated:

“At a local authority level? Less so, largely because the adjoining local authorities, particularly Donegal County Council and Derry City and Strabane District Council, work so collaboratively on a sub-regional basis anyway [...]” (Interview 1, August 2023).

And:

“I guess the border has to go somewhere. [...] Where people think the border should go is actually irrelevant to what needs to happen across the border” (Interview 3, August 2023).

The management of Lough Foyle has been under the jurisdiction of the Foyle Fisheries Commission and, subsequently, the Loughs Agency since 1952. When placing this historical context of cross-border collaboration - via a jointly sponsored management body - alongside the call for integrative and holistic management of Lough Foyle or the *“what needs to happen”* (Interview 3, August 2023), a clear path forward emerges by reflecting on past practices: sub-regional cross-border collaboration.

Such collaboration has significantly increased since the signing of the Good Friday Agreement in 1998. Notably, this has been further formalized through joint legislation in 2007 and strengthened through more structured sub-regional initiatives, such as the establishment of the *Northwest Strategic Growth Partnership* in 2014 (Interviews 1 and 3), *“[a] local government-led partnership for the area [...]”* (Interview 3, August 2023), as a participant states.

Although the *Northwest Strategic Growth Partnership* has no direct jurisdiction over Lough Foyle, its sub-regional collaborative work has the potential to cultivate a *“shared spatial imaginary”* (Sohn, 2014, p. 598). This, described in Sohn’s (2014) cross-border integration model termed the *“Territorial Project”* (see [Table 3](#)), emphasizes cross-border integration and can result in the convergence of both sides of the border through mutual understanding and trust. Herein, the border space transforms into a platform for gathering and sharing (Sohn, 2014).

Table 3: Sohn’s (2014) Type 2 model of cross-border integration with the authors emphasis in italics (Source: modified from Sohn, 2014)

	Type 2 „Territorial Project“
Main Objective	<i>Place-making</i>
Key variables	<i>Non-tangible variables: mutual learning capacities, common understanding, trust, sense of belonging</i>
Domains concerned	<i>Culture (arts, languages, traditions, identities), Spatial planning, Economic</i>

	positioning, territorial marketing, Knowledge-intensive activities, <i>Cross-border residential mobility</i>
Type of interactions	Knowledge interactions, Ideational ties (<i>mutual affection, feeling of cohesion, sense of belonging</i>)
Willingness of public authorities to cooperate	Essential
Purpose of cross-border cooperation	<i>Identity-providing</i> (gaining public awareness and mobilization, building a shared spatial imaginary, a common territorial identity)

By extending this mutual trust and understanding at a sub-regional level, the *Lough Foyle Space* could overcome its current dispute of tenure and instead focus on what truly matters for the region and its communities. This approach requires to keep on working simultaneously on fostering mutual trust and understanding through initiatives like the *Northwest Strategic Growth Partnership*, alongside institutional collaboration through entities such as the *Loughs Agency*. These examples represent just two of the most obvious pathways to achieve such a transformation. Table 3 offers additional insight into the “*Territorial Project*”. It presents options for how Lough Foyle could be reimagined as a space for gathering and sharing. By placing emphasis on the *non-tangible variables* – such as a *sense of belonging*, which *Lough Foyle* could provide - a *willingness to cooperate between (local) public authorities* can emerge, enabling the realization of the *place-making* objective. Or in the words of a participant:

"It's more than the debate around the jurisdiction and the Foyle. Let the two States work that out. We'll continue to operate in terms of looking after the place and the people that live in the place" (Interview 1, August 2023).

"Looking after the place" (Interview 1, August 2023) can refer to regulating potentially negative externalities arising from economic development, such as Pacific Oyster aquaculture, while also ensuring economic prosperity, the shared mentality as well as people’s spatial mobility and livelihoods in the *Lough Foyle Space*. Additionally, in consideration of the population size of the “*Northwest City Region*”, a participant noted that this population could potentially reach a *"[...] critical mass where the border is less relevant [...]"* (Interview 1, August 2023), and is succinctly articulated in a previous quote from a participant who states:

"[B]ecause we see what benefits Derry benefits Donegal. [...] I always use the example that if you looked at the car park for one of the main employers in the town, Seagate, just on the edge of the city, there's around half of the car park with Donegal registrations" (Interview 1, August 2023).

So, when considering borders in the *Lough Foyle Space*, there is evidence of cross-border collaboration and of borders functioning as spaces of connection. This is aptly summarized by one participant, who states:

"I like to think there are more opportunities than boundaries [borders]" (Interview 1, August 2023).

Thus, in seeing borders not as merely divisive entities, but rather as complex constructed spatial phenomena that operate across multiple scales, we can understand them as connecting "political, social, economic, technological, cultural and psychological processes", as Laine (2021, pp. 182–183) highlights. In *Lough Foyle Space* compelling evidence can be found to suggest that borders can act as connectors "in space, in time and at the level of everyday life" (Laine, 2021, p. 183).

Additionally, the importance of scale when dealing with borders and boundaries cannot be overstated. While certain approaches may work effectively on a local level, they might fail to translate to a national or international level. This issue is explored further in the final Section 5.7 'Useful' boundaries, where this thesis discusses the importance of scale in relation to borders and boundaries, while also providing an examination of the existing boundaries within *the Lough Foyle Space* and how these provide deeper insights into the mismatches at play.

5.7 'Useful' boundaries

The impact of borders in the *Lough Foyle Space* proves notably complex, as their relevance is either diminished through cross-border collaboration (see Section 5.6 *Borders, Spaces of connection*) or rendered inapplicable due to the inherent fluidity of Lough Foyle itself (see Section 5.5 *Wet borders*). While borders may hold limited meaning in this space, boundaries - "whether actual or conceptual" (Sternlieb et al., 2013, p. 119) - emerge as crucial elements that both shape and are shaped by this social-ecological system. The construction of the *Lough Foyle Space* as a watery boundary draws attention to its own agency, including its depth and motion, while also highlighting its inherent temporalities (Kanesu, 2024). The social construction and agency are substantiated by participants' responses to the question, "What does your group perceive as a boundary?" (see Table 1).

Participants identified multiple boundaries which are not borders within the *Lough Foyle Space*, which bound both habitats and physico-chemical characteristics of the lough. These boundaries, owing to their liquid nature and/or vast extent, operate largely beyond immediate human control (Kanesu, 2024). The boundaries manifest in various forms and span various scales: geographical distinctions such as the 'near shore' and 'outer shore' demarcations relevant to wind craft parks (Interview 1, August 2023); hydrological boundaries exemplified by the River Foyle's catchment area (Interview 7, December 2023); and the dynamic interface between river and lough characterized by salinity gradients and tidal movements (Interview 6, September 2023). Lough Foyle as an intertidal transitional water body in constant flux creates temporal boundaries between land and sea through tidal movements (Interview 7, December 2023). Moreover, while the lough as a whole forms a physical boundary between shoreline

communities, its water column exhibits internal boundaries through vertical stratification, evidenced by both salinity and temperature gradients (Interview 7, December 2023 and Interview 6, September 2023).

The dynamism of Lough Foyle's intertidal ecosystem challenges binary distinctions between land and sea, as these boundaries remain in perpetual flux (Ryan, 2016). As Sammler (2019) notes when "drawing a finite boundary that can define a coastline" (p. 606), "the relationships between land and sea [...] exhibits the unresolved tensions between them, as the categorization is dependent upon the scales with which they are engaged" (p. 607). This refers to the *Coastline Paradox*, where a coastline's measured length varies according to the length of the measuring device (Sammler, 2019), emphasizing how the scales with which we engage the sea fundamentally shapes the definitions of the *what* and the *when* in our understanding of land or sea, assuming a clear distinction is even possible. Thus, the notion of being 'inside the Venn diagram' is once more applicable. Not 'purely' sea and not 'purely' land, sitting "in between those 'safe and useful' spaces" (Choi, 2022, p. 346) when looking at it from a binary land- or sea-based perspective. Adopting Steinberg and Peters' (2015) 'wet ontology' - or Choi's (2022) 'slippery ontology' – and acknowledging this inherent in-betweenness of the *Lough Foyle Space*, might be more appropriate than attempting to define the boundaries with precision (Choi, 2022). And while the exact demarcation of boundaries may be a seemingly intangible goal, the *Lough Foyle Space* nonetheless contains recognizable and meaningful boundaries.

A participant summarized them:

"We do recognize that there's a boundary between the waters in terms of the riverine waters that are inputting into Lough Foyle, the estuary itself and then the tide movement from the ocean waters and the seawaters end at the mouth of Lough Foyle. There's a boundary there in terms of the oceanographics and the physical makeup of the water itself and the water quality and chemistry. There are chemical boundaries there in terms of salinity that controls some of our species and habitats that we see" (Interview 6, September 2023).

Adding that:

"Whether we view it as a boundary and in what terms we view it as a boundary. Very much, I think, our thoughts would be on the environment, on the ecosystem and where the boundaries within the ecosystem come into play, be that physical boundaries in terms of barriers to species and habitats and their movement within the Lough or, as I say, the more physical, chemical boundaries in terms of salinity barriers and water temperature barriers and that type of thing. Those are boundaries that we would monitor and that we would, I suppose, experience on our day-to-day work [...] when we're observing these fisheries and we're monitoring them" (Interview 6, September 2023).

And a participant acknowledges that,

"a lot of the boundaries we have are not particularly legal" (Interview 8, January 2024).

So, the boundaries found in the *Lough Foyle Space* are not borders. They cannot be legally enforced or are not backed by formal law and are the boundaries of the ecosystem itself. These are the boundaries which management should encompass.

A participant explains:

"[A] boundary should be, and I suppose taking it out of the legal sense, it's bounding where you manage" (Interview 8, January 2024).

Adding:

"So, to me, the boundary should be for a purpose" (Interview 8, January 2024).

And concluding:

"And I think given we're talking about a natural system, then the boundaries have to be of that natural system rather than based on jurisdiction" (Interview 8, January 2024).

The preceding analysis reveals that borders hold limited significance in this context, while suggesting the need for alternative boundaries bounding the ecological system rather than geopolitical interests. Although a 'slippery ontology' problematizes precise boundary definition (Choi, 2022), well-defined physical boundaries may remain essential for effective spatial management (Ostrom, 2009). This tension between fluid ecological realities and management needs manifests in the above calls to align jurisdictional boundaries with the 'natural' boundaries of the *Lough Foyle Space*. Such alignment resonates with various cross-border integrated management approaches - including ecosystem-based management (EBM), integrated coastal zone management (ICZM) and the "notion of a 'sea interests'"³⁴ (Ritchie & and Ellis, 2010, p. 718).

Ultimately, these approaches challenge what Chilla et al. (2012) describe as the "territorial dimension of sovereignty as such" (p. 963), suggesting a fundamental reimagining of governance in fluid environments. The historical governance approaches to marine space illustrates this process of *de-territorialization*. Steinberg (1999) describes an oscillation between two contradictory tendencies in marine governance. The impulse to enclose seas and the conceptualization of oceans as "friction-free space" (Steinberg, 1999, p. 259). And while *de-territorialization* processes are taking place within the 'third phase' of enclosures - marked by the increasing involvement of non-state actors - *re-territorialization* gains prominence in contexts where enclosure mechanisms effectively transform "'the commons' and their resources into bounded spaces and property" (Lambach, 2020, p. 3). This transformation enables systems characterized by "legibility, control and resource exploitation" (Lambach, 2020, p. 3).

³⁴ See Ritchie et al. (2022) and (Ritchie & and Ellis, 2010) for their call for a single managing marine body in Lough Foyle with the 'sea interest' in mind.

Steinberg (1999) summarizes this quite succinctly, when stating that “[l]ines may be drawn -or erased- in order to promote a range of social alternatives in global ocean space” (p. 255). Then the question arises of what needs to be considered when (re)drawing lines or boundaries in the *Lough Foyle Space*?

Here this thesis argues that the levels of the scale on which these new boundaries are drawn play a crucial role in understanding the *spatial mismatches* within the *Lough Foyle Space*, particularly in relation to its fluid boundaries and the current governance challenges surrounding the topic of Pacific Oyster aquafarming.

A notable *spatial mismatch* manifests in the disparity between international and local governance approaches. While ownership disputes between Northern Ireland and the Republic of Ireland persist at the national level and are characterized by an absence of tenure negotiations (Ansong, 2021), a contrasting pattern emerges at the local level. Here, stakeholders demonstrate effective cross-border collaboration, working to harmonize policies pertaining to the *Lough Foyle Space* despite the higher-level jurisdictional impasse.

This is stated by a participant when asked about having an exact location of the border:

"At a local authority level? Less so, [...]" (Interview 1, August 2023).

I revisit this answer to emphasize that the exact location of the border is not a prerequisite for this stakeholder to manage the *Lough Foyle Space* in a collaborative and holistic, ‘one ecosystem’ manner. Indeed, at the local level, collaboration effectively bridges any potential mismatch between ecological and jurisdictional spaces. However, the presence of unregulated Pacific Oyster aquaculture, with its potential detrimental environmental impacts, reveals a *spatial mismatch* in the *Lough Foyle Space* anyway.

This *spatial mismatch* emerges from the divergence between local and (inter)national interests. Specifically, international geopolitical interests at the national level misalign with local cross-border collaborative efforts. These national governments prioritize the construction of their territory over both the ‘needs’ of the social-ecological system and existing local cross-border collaboration. This *spatial mismatch* exemplifies what has been described as a "tug of war between agency and structural processes" (Brunet-Jailly 2011 in Tripathi & Chaturvedi, 2020, p. 178). In other words, the bottom-up collaborative efforts (in Brunet-Jailly’s words: *agency*) clash at some level along the scale with the top-down ‘fixed’ structures of governmental frameworks, the *structural processes*.

Given that borders are inherently tied to territory, addressing non-territorial issues - such as Pacific Oyster aquaculture licensing³⁵ - necessitates the need to think across multiple scales (e.g. temporal, institutional, spatial, etc.) and to move beyond the predominance of national territory. This is particularly crucial in multi-scaled contexts like the *Lough Foyle Space*, where effective governance requires more nuanced approaches to spatial management (Chilla et al., 2012).

³⁵ The current situation represents a fundamentally functional issue, as the non-regulation of Lough Foyle's foreshore has created an effectively non-territorial space where neither state can exercise sovereign power (Agnew 1994), shifting the focus from territorial claims to practical governance needs.

Thus, the abstract notion of questioning where the exact point in a hierarchical system lies at which local interests are overshadowed by national ones - especially in contexts where cross-border cooperation is rarely a political mandate (Chilla et al., 2012) and boundary definitions remain an inexact science (Choi, 2022) - highlights the logic of moving away from national territorialities in the *Lough Foyle Space*. Instead, competences should rest with regional or local (cross-border) institutions (Chilla et al., 2012). In the absence of an institutionalized cross-border mandate at regional or local levels, informal cross-border collaboration must take on a more critical role to avoid falling into the *territorial trap* (Agnew, 1994).

5.8 Conclusion

In summary, two-dimensional borders are inadequate for capturing the complex, three-dimensional materiality of the *Lough Foyle Space* (Steinberg & Peters, 2015). Furthermore, the level at which borders and boundaries are drawn, and how they interact with spatial, temporal, and institutional scales, significantly influences their effects on social-ecological systems (Borges, accepted). As a result, rigid, 'landed' logics of bordering and zoning are less effective at addressing dynamic and fluid spaces (Peters, 2020). There is, therefore, a pressing need to rethink and overcome the ontological boundaries of how ecosystems and protected areas are conceptualized and managed.

With the conclusion of this chapter, and through the integration of intradisciplinary literature and critical examination of existing research on Lough Foyle combined with the firsthand responses of the participants, this study has identified specific and novel understandings of borders and boundaries within *Lough Foyle Space*. These insights open new ways to approach the *de-territorialization* of (marine) governance. In the final chapter of this thesis, *Chapter 6. Conclusion*, I bridge the gap between the localized, microscopic understandings of boundaries within the *Lough Foyle Space* and broader theoretical discussions on *de-territorialization* processes in (marine) governance. The following chapter also highlights the continued need for ontological shifts towards more de-territorialized frameworks of governance.

6 Conclusion

This thesis has brought focused attention to local instances of *spatial mismatch*, while simultaneously contributing to a broader understanding of border and boundary dynamics within social-ecological systems (SES), particularly in contested marine spaces. In this context, it is worth revisiting a statement made by one participant, who noted that

“a lot of the boundaries we have are not particularly legal” (Interview 8, January 2024),

Showing that, especially against the backdrop of resurgent border controls in Europe - such as the temporary reintroduction of border controls by many countries in the European Union (*European Commission*, n.d.) – ‘legal’ borders continue to dominate and reflect the strategic interests of nation states (Hung, 2025). This reinforces the argument made in *Section 5.7 ‘Useful’ boundaries* about the persistent prioritization of territory over lived realities and agency of communities inhabiting cross-border regions. Accordingly, this chapter offers insights into how and why ontological shifts in our understanding of governance can provide pathways toward more inclusive and resilient futures.

The final chapter is structured as follows. It begins with a summary of the preceding chapters before reconnecting to the research rationales established in *Chapter 2. Introduction*. Subsequently, the study's limitations are acknowledged while lanes for future research that could extend and deepen this work are identified. The chapter concludes by articulating the key contributions of this thesis.

6.1 Summary of Chapters

Chapter 2. Introduction establishes boundaries as the dominant paradigm in modern spatial management while highlighting their critical role in the social-ecological systems approaches. The chapter challenges conventional two-dimensional cartographic representations for their failure to capture spatial complexity. Applying this to *Lough Foyle Space* frames the two key rationales which initially guided this research: first, that resolving existing *spatial mismatches* would require a formal ‘agreement’ between United Kingdom (UK) and the Republic of Ireland (ROI) on the precise border location; and second, that borders constrain connections between communities on either side of the border.

Chapter 3. Literature Review then synthesizes the diverse theoretical frameworks that inform this thesis. This thesis draws from boundary and border studies, incorporating various geographical disciplines, while also engaging with scholarship on social-ecological systems. Through a critical review of existing research on Lough Foyle, this chapter identified significant gaps in current understanding. While Lough Foyle has been extensively studied, this thesis offers a novel analytical approach by examining this space through the lens of boundaries. By critically engaging with established concepts of boundaries and borders, this research bridges an important gap between global theoretical frameworks and the localized manifestation of boundary dynamics in marine spaces.

The next chapter, *Chapter 4. Methods*, establishes the methodological foundation for this research by introducing the study area and research approach. *Section 4.2 Ethics* underpins the importance of ethics in this study, particularly emphasizing the necessary ethical considerations of reflexive research

practices. The chapter then provides a detailed characterization of *Lough Foyle Space*, encompassing its geographical extent and historical context, while explaining the research team's rationale for selecting this site. This is followed by an outline of the stakeholder identification process, the data collection strategy and the data analysis process. Given that the extensive data collected exceeds the scope of a master's thesis, this section also justifies the selective focus of the analysis. This chapter concludes with a description of a feedback mechanism for the stakeholders interviewed.

Chapter 5. Results and Discussion, provides an in-depth analysis of the interview data focusing on two key concepts: boundaries and borders. The analysis centers on interviewees' responses regarding their perceived importance of reaching an 'agreement' between the Republic of Ireland and the United Kingdom on the exact location of the border that separates the two States in Lough Foyle. *Section 5.2 Multilevel constructions and mismatches in Lough Foyle Space* discusses how the construction of nation states and borders lead to *spatial mismatches*, while *Section 5.3 Borders without boundaries: Pragmatism and the border* then reveals multiple *spatial mismatches* within the study area. The first mismatch emerges between official policy frameworks and lived realities. The second manifests between the understanding of the border in everyday life and its 'reality' on a map. *Sections 5.4 Borders, Disruptors* and *5.6 Borders, Spaces of connection* explore different aspects of borders in the *Lough Foyle Space*. While borders can disrupt various human flows and relationships, they also serve as human spaces of connection and collaboration. This disruptive aspect of borders on human activities does not extend to more-than-human entities.

In *Section 5.5 'Wet Borders'* this thesis explores the necessity of adopting a 'wet ontology' (Steinberg & Peters, 2015) and applies it to the boundaries found in the *Lough Foyle Space* in *Section 5.7 'Useful Boundaries'*. To address existing *spatial mismatches*, this thesis proposes to allow ecosystems boundaries to overlap and function across, over and through national borders in *Lough Foyle Space*. Additionally, this thesis argues that managing cross-border ecosystems requires careful consideration of the multiple scales and levels they exist in.

6.2 Reconnecting with the research rationales

The analysis presented in this thesis demonstrates that adherence to the research rationales outlined in *Chapter 2. Introduction* yields only partial insight. The first rationale - resolving *spatial mismatches* in the *Lough Foyle Space* would require a formal 'agreement' between the Republic of Ireland and the United Kingdom on the precise location of the border - is reconsidered in light of the findings. As discussed in *Section 5.3 Borders without boundaries: Pragmatism and the border*, while an 'agreement' is indeed necessary to enable the licensing and regulation of Pacific Oyster aquaculture, the critical issue is not the precise demarcation of the border. Rather, it concerns how management should be coordinated - ideally through a single managing entity. In this sense, a fixed border is not required in the *Lough Foyle Space*; what is 'needed', is a pragmatic governance arrangement that transcends rigid territorial delineation.

Regarding the second research rationale, the analysis reveals a more nuanced picture, as it requires careful consideration of which *spaces* are affected — or unaffected — when asserting that borders disrupt connections. As explored in sections 5.6 *Borders, Spaces of connection* and 5.4 *Borders, Disruptors*, borders can both inhibit and enable interactions, depending on the specific *space* under consideration. Notably, the findings indicate that *Lough Foyle Space* functions more as a space of connection than of disruption, challenging common assumptions about the fragmenting effects of borders in cross-border contexts.

Furthermore, the results show that Lough Foyle is a coastal, intertidal body of water, where the traditionally assumed binary division between land and sea dissolves. This challenges conventional – territorial - approaches to marine governance based on ‘static zones’. Instead, this thesis advocates for a new conceptualization of (marine) governance in cross-border spaces towards what Steinberg and Peters (2015) coin a ‘wet ontology’.

6.3 Limitations and future directions

As previously noted, this thesis utilizes only a subset of the data collected during the research process. The remaining data presents significant opportunities for future research and could serve as a foundation for several additional research directions, including, but not limited to, 1) expanding the initiated social network analysis to provide quantitative insights into the dynamics of the social system within this social-ecological system. 2) Conducting an in-depth historical investigation of borders and boundaries in the *Lough Foyle Space* to enhance understanding of the processes that formed and form the *Lough Foyle Space*. 3) Exploring additional themes, including stakeholder perspectives on management and collaboration, through expanded interviews to develop a more comprehensive understanding of social and ecological processes. And while this thesis gives a ‘microscopic’ view of some stakeholder perspectives on boundaries and borders in *Lough Foyle Space*, the absence of Pacific Oyster aquafarmer perspectives represents a significant limitation, suggesting that current findings remain inchoate and warrant further investigation.

Such extensions would contribute to a more complete understanding of this complex social-ecological system. Further investigation would provide valuable opportunities to examine both current and emerging issues from multiple theoretical and methodological perspectives, potentially revealing innovative governance solutions that generate mutual benefits for all stakeholders involved.

6.4 Contributions

Nonetheless and in spite of its limitations, this research contributes to broader theoretical discussions on *de-territorialization* processes in (marine) governance, specifically bridging the gap between the global theoretical frameworks and local manifestations of boundary dynamics in marine spaces. So, this empirical work gives a more nuanced understanding of boundaries and the associated effects and processes in *Lough Foyle Space*.

Drawing on recent scholarship (Peters, 2020; Peters & Turner, 2025a; Taylor, 2023), this research contributes to further documenting the need for an ontological shift away from a territorial ontology

towards a (marine) governance, which is *de-territorialized*, and in which one thinks 'outside the box'. At the global level, Peters (2020) and Steinberg (1999) already demonstrate the necessity of challenging territorial ontologies. And while nation states already struggle to address environmental and climate crisis issues in their own jurisdiction, these challenges intensify in cross-border ecosystems, particularly given that approximately half of all marine borders remain disputed (Østhagen, 2021). Current management practices and strategies, rooted in territorial ontologies, rely on 'static zones' to delineate the space managed. These demarcation lines halt at the neighboring nation states' territory, disregarding the continuous nature of ecosystems that extend beyond political borders (Taylor, 2023). In the local context of the *Lough Foyle Space*, this research shows that thinking with territorial ontologies generates *spatial mismatches* between jurisdictional and environmental spaces and the drawn political borders, which do not coincide with the boundaries of the ecosystem. Thus, ontological shifts away from territorial ontologies in local contexts is as necessary as in global contexts.

Ontological shifts fundamentally transform how we conceptualize and interact with phenomena. Peters (2020) identifies several pathways to facilitate such transformations, including a "listening to new narratives [and] an openness to future scenarios" (p. 6). So, we need not only interrogate the "current problems, possible solutions, needed science and desired policy interventions" but also "the modes of thinking and the [...] ontologies, that inform these" (Peters, 2020, p. 8).

I propose a fundamental shift away from ontologies that constrain contemporary governance practices - particularly territory as the "assumed ontology driving oceanic control" (Peters, 2020, p. 8; Lambach, 2020) - toward management approaches which prioritize ecosystem boundaries over political borders. And while Ostrom (2009) establishes that governance requires boundaries, scholars like Choi (2022) and Taylor (2023) argue these need not - and perhaps cannot - be rigidly defined, nor should they necessarily align with nation-state borders. This shift means to consider that Earth is a 'wet' planet. So, the earthly and 'landed' ontology of territory also needs to be challenged considering Earth's inherent 'wetness'.

Additionally, the global level is not the only level at which "global environmental governance takes place" (Bulkeley, 2005, p. 879) and thus the nation state is not the only level where such ontologies should be shifted, as human activity is not bound to just the nation state level (Taylor, 2023). This multilevel approach to ontological shifts can manifest in concepts like Taylor's (2023) *regionalization*. Here the author suggests defining "regions of risk, not with neat boundaries like states, but with clear expanses of risk circumscribed by declining probabilities of said risk" (Taylor, 2023, p. 66). These regions integrate resilient components defined by social processes with sustainable elements shaped by physical processes, which "locates humans as part of nature" (Taylor, 2023, p. 68). The possibilities for ontological shifts are manifold and should be tailored to the specific regional contexts, perhaps through the involvement of "a more diverse and intersectional range of voices and bodies into these discussions" (Jackman et al., 2020, p. 8) and from "those whose worlds are already oceanic and entangled with the seas" (Peters & Turner, 2025a, p. 279).

This thesis argues that evidence of ontological shifts in *Lough Foyle Space* is already emerging through the implementation of a cross-border management institution, the Loughs Agency. It manages the fisheries and shellfisheries in Lough Foyle and Carlingford Lough and their respective catchments. With both loughs being officially disputed spaces, this is a significant departure from traditional territorial governance and the Loughs Agency embodies a pragmatic transcendence of national territorial claims. This arrangement demonstrates how both Nations, in the context of salmon fisheries in Lough Foyle, have prioritized regional needs over territorial sovereignty disputes. This case illustrates a nuanced approach to transboundary resource management that moves beyond reductive binary categorizations of jurisdiction toward a model of shared stewardship and mutual benefit.

A second ontological shift manifests through the evolving “sense of connectedness” (Interview 3, August 2023) within the *Lough Foyle Space*. This transformation is characterized by a possible reconfiguration of identity from national affiliation towards a regional consciousness centered on Lough Foyle. This is particularly evident in the emergence of the *Northwest City Region* concept. This shift demonstrates how human activities and identities can meaningfully transcend national boundaries, creating new spatial understandings that better reflect lived experiences and regional connections.

Both ongoing shifts exemplify de-territorialization by redirecting focus from jurisdictional ownership toward regional interests and their facilitation. A holistic management approach to Lough Foyle - including a licensed and regulated Pacific Oyster aquafarming - further diminishes the importance of precise maritime border demarcation. This approach helps mitigate the adverse effects of *spatial mismatches* and ‘landed’ ontologies, which are evident in the complex issue of unlicensed Pacific Oyster aquaculture operations within these contested waters.

In conclusion, ontologies are deeply embedded in the ways we conceptualize and practice environmental and anthropogenic climate change management and resilience and the inadequacy of traditional approaches necessitates new modes of thinking. However, as Choi (2022) cautions, adherence to “any singular and rigid knowledge” (p. 355) risks falling into what Agnew (1994) terms the ‘territorial trap.’ Nonetheless, the reality that anthropogenic climate change does not respect humanly constructed political borders provides compelling impetus to think differently about current and coming issues.

7 References

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8 Appendix

Complete Interview schedule

Primary Questions	Main themes	Follow-up questions
Who do you represent?	Classification	What is the background of the members?
		Under which administration does [group name] fall?
What are the activities of your group in the Lough Foyle area?	Activities and Ecological features	Can you describe the importance of Lough Foyle to [group]
		Are there any activities of other groups or organisations that affect [group name] activities directly?
		Could you split up Lough Foyle into decisive eco logical or natural features? If so, which features?
		Is [group name] interested in the whole Lough or just parts of it? If only parts, which ones?
		Do you think it is possible to manage parts of the Lough separately?
What does your group perceive as a boundary?	Boundaries	
Are there any boundary or border issues?	Boundaries	Is it important for [group name] to have a border in this area?
		Could a (Marine) Protected Area be a solution to boundary issues?
		How would you imagine the activities to change, if there is a set border?
Are there cross border meetings/projects/initiatives, that you know of? If so, do any members of your group attend them regularly?	Transboundary connections and activities	How long have there been these meetings and since when does your group attend them?
		Do you have the feeling that your group is well informed on the activities and regulations regarding Lough Foyle?
What does your group consider as good collaboration?	Time	Is there a temporal element to good collaboration?
		Has Brexit changed anything in the management of the Lough Foyle area?
		Are there any temporal markers, besides Brexit, which affected management in Lough Foyle?

Application form of the Ethics Commission

EK-Antrag Borges 7.6.2022 – überarbeitet, Drs.Nr.EK/2022/053

Antrag auf Stellungnahme der Kommission für Forschungsfolgenabschätzung und Ethik

1. Bezeichnung des Forschungsvorhabens

Connectivity of Social Networks and Ecosystem Services for Transboundary Coastal-Marine Spatial Planning

2. Name und Kontaktdaten des Antragstellers¹ (Dienstanschrift):

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¹ Im Fall von studentischen Abschlussarbeiten muss der betreuende Hochschullehrer mit als Antragsteller auftreten und den Antrag mit unterschreiben

3. Angaben zu den Rahmenbedingungen des Vorhabens

Es handelt sich um einen Antrag auf Finanzierung durch HIFMB (internal Helmholtz funding).

Eine Stellungnahme der Ethikkommission wird nicht verlangt.

Die Datenerhebungen finden im Zeitraum von 01. August 2022 bis 31. Dezember 2024.

Empirical research consisting of secondary data analysis, interviews, and participant observation will take place from 01 August 2022.

There are three study areas: mangrove co-managed areas in north Brazil, coastal-marine areas on the border between the Republic of Ireland and Northern Ireland (UK), and Antarctica (more specifically, the Weddell Sea and its proposed marine protected area). Some aspects of the methods will vary between the areas.

Part of the research will occur online due to the pandemic and also to support environmentally-friendly research practice where unnecessary travel (and, therefore, CO₂ emissions) is avoided.

Whenever possible, interviews will be conducted remotely via the university's communications platform, BBB, using a secure code to enter the room. However, in northern Brazil, technical capacity for online interviews is very limited for most participants. Therefore, in-person interaction will likely have to be preferred.

Informed consent (see below) will be obtained for the purpose of interviews and recording.

Participant observation will occur during online and face-to-face events that might happen independently of this research project, for example, the meetings of the Commission for the Conservation of Antarctic Marine Living Resources (CCAMLR) in Hobart, Australia. However, further details about this specific aspect will be decided upon as events are announced and participation by the researcher(s) is arranged. In the cases where online and in-person participation is possible, remote participation will be favored, but only where the necessary interaction with research participants is not hindered.

Even though, as a researcher, the proponents of this research project are part of a group of actors (academia) that has, at least, indirect stake in the decisions around conservation and protected areas in general, the proponents do not have any private interest in any decision-making processes that will be investigated by this study or that the participants in this research might be directly or indirectly involved. The proponents' interests lie solely in generating evidenced-based knowledge and making recommendations, based on the results, that will bring the most social-ecological benefits, through the lenses of environmental justice and human and non-human rights.

4. Gegenstand und Verfahren des Vorhabens

Gegenstand.

Spatial mismatches occur, for example, when the governance actions happen at spatial levels that do not reflect those of the problem that these actions aim to tackle. In other words, spatial mismatches reflect misalignments between the social and ecological elements of social-ecological systems, considering a variety of scales, such as time, (Euclidean) space, institutions, etc. Here it is important to explain how the terms “level” and “scale” are understood in the framework of this project. The definition of scale in Gibson et al. 2000² is adopted here, where “scale” refers to “the spatial, temporal, quantitative, or analytical dimensions used to measure and study any phenomenon”. “Level”, on the other hand, is described by these same authors as “the units of analysis that are located at different positions on a scale”. For example, when considering the (Euclidean) spatial scale, cities would represent lower spatial levels when compared to countries. In this study, however, we take on a broader definition of “space”, and consider the various dimensions of space, such as the Euclidean (or sometimes referred to as “geographical”) space, the social (or human) space, which refers to the different connections between human social actors and how they interact in various ways, for example, through communication and collaboration, and the more-than-human social space, which refers to the manifold interactions between humans and non-humans.

This broader definition of space allows us to identify as spatial mismatch situation in environmental governance such as the case in which local actors (social system) who are heavily dependent on certain ecosystems (ecological system) are excluded from the governance arrangements and planning processes in these areas. Such a mismatch can be inspected through an analysis of the different networks that make up a certain social-ecological system. An example of a (human) social network is the connections formed by different stakeholder groups when they collaborate in a given conservation endeavor, e.g. the management of a protected area. The connections between (human) user groups (e.g. fishers) and the ecosystems from which they obtain their livelihoods (e.g. specific fishing grounds) form a more-than-human network.

Local actors that will be interviewed are local, direct resource users (fishers, fish farmers, small tourism operators, etc.), members of academia (university staff and other researchers), representatives of federal, state, or municipality administration, and employees at NGOs and associations that work directly in the study areas.

Social network analysis represents a well-established methods field in graph studies that can be used to investigate various elements of these networks that characterize how strongly or weakly connected different stakeholders are, which stakeholders can be considered “brokers” or “gatekeepers” and which stakeholders might not be linked to other in governance arrangements. Similarly, such an analysis can include non-human elements, such as ecosystems, in

² Gibson, C. C., E. Ostrom, and T. K. Ahn. 2000. The concept of scale and the human dimensions of global change: a survey. *Ecological Economics* 32(2):217–239

which case they are usually referred to as Social-Ecological Network Analysis (SENA). SENA methods involve surveys that gauge the connections among stakeholders drawn from a pre-made list but, for this study, will also include participatory mapping, which is a general term that encompasses approaches and techniques that combine tools of cartography and participatory methods to investigate spatial knowledge.

The overall aim of this project is to assess spatial mismatches and investigate how flows and boundaries shape social-ecological connectivity and form networks relating to effective management:

- 1) What are the possible weak links/relationships of the networks of stakeholders considering the spatial dynamics of resource use?;
- 2) How could knowledge on the flows of people, ecosystem services, and biodiversity feed into this diagnosis?;
- 3) Where and how can social networks be strengthened to increase the chances of successful adaptive planning and implementation of, and compliance with, spatial management strategies at local and regional levels?

Methoden. SENA will be used to explore whether these networks constrain or enable key social processes, considering also how social units interact not only among themselves but also with ecological units. The methods consist of three main tools: Interviews, analysis of secondary data, and observations, will be used to obtain the data that will feed the construction of these multi-level, social-ecological networks.

"Interviews" in this research project will consist of three methods/phases: 1) participatory mapping; 2) social-ecological network survey; and 3) open-ended questions. Interviews will happen on a one-to-one basis (only one participant at a time); however, the interactions might happen in a small-group if relevant.

Another method of interaction in this research project is participant observation, which will likely take place at in-person events such as the 2022 CCAMLR meeting in Hobart, Australia. Participant observation will take place with the consent of the relevant body, e.g., CCAMLR.

Additionally, retribution events may be organized, either in-person or online, to ensure that participants can review and provide input on the preliminary findings of the research. There may be more than one retribution event, if necessary. These events can include discussions where participants actively engage with the findings, share their perspectives, and suggest improvements. This interactive approach helps to refine the research outcomes and ensures that the participants' voices are integral to the process. This approach will subsequently be referred to as "data collection" or "further data collection."

These events will be held only if there is interest from the participants. This means that participants will be contacted beforehand to discuss if they are interested in this form of feedback about the work, how this feedback can take place, and if they consent that the discussion is

used to further assess the data so far. Should respondents from the initial phase of data collection express interest in receiving this feedback, retribution events can also be conducted without any further data collection, if the participants so prefer. Alternative forms of feedback will also be offered, such as a policy brief or the paper produced out of this research. The participants will also be informed about events where these results will be presented, giving them the opportunity to attend the events, in case it is possible, and discuss the results with one of the researchers involved. Independently of the format of the feedback, any interaction between researchers and interviewees will only be further included in the analysis with explicit consent from the interviewee.

The retribution events will guarantee anonymity, ensure data protection, and require informed consent for data collection from all participants. If necessary, discussions will be held in small groups to facilitate more effective communication, or even with only one or two people, if so desired by the person interviewed in the first phase of data collection. It will be ensured that a comfortable and confidential atmosphere is created, in which participants are informed in advance of who will be in attendance and who will be present.

In these events, results will be presented in a way that it is not revealed, and cannot be deduced, who the respondents from the collection phase were. This will be done by, for example, showing results from groups from which several members could have potentially been part of the initial data collection. At the outset of the session, participants will be informed that, should individuals who participated in the previous phase be present in the group, they are not required to disclose their participation or responses. Furthermore, participants will be instructed not to inquire about the identities of respondents.

Experimentelle Aufgaben. The participatory mapping involves asking participants to draw on a piece of paper the local ecosystems that are important to them. They will be asked specifically to point to the areas that are suppliers of benefits from nature ("ecosystem services"). During this phase, the participant will be asked about their perceptions regarding these benefits (e.g., how important they are to them and to others) and about the governance of these benefits and of the ecosystems that provide them, which means that this phase also entails open-ended questions.

The social-network survey is based on a previously gathered list of participants and/or organizations, selected based on the review of the relevant literature and other documentation ("gray literature"). The participant will be asked if they communicate and/or collaborate with each person/organization on the list. They will also be asked to rank how well this communication and/or collaboration works specifically for conservation initiatives. In this way, the network will show which actors collaborate and/or communicate with which other actors and how successful this interaction is in terms of marine governance.

A similar method is used for the ecological elements. Based on a list of local ecosystems, participants are asked 1) if they directly interact with each ecosystem on the list; 2) what the nature of the interaction is (here some of options will be offered - e.g., extraction, research,

conflict - , as well as the option "other"); 3) how strong this interaction is; and 4) how this interaction is connected to conservation and marine governance.

Finally, other open-ended questions will be asked to further investigate any points of interest that were raised by the participant in the first two phases, e.g., "Why did you mention this specific interaction?".

Durchführung. Interviews will be conducted either in English (Isle of Ireland and Antarctica) or in Portuguese. Besides Dr. Rebecca Borges, collaborators will be trained and tasked with conducting some of the interviews and taking part in events for the participant observation interactions, in case relevant events happen and participation by the researchers and collaborators is possible.

Auswertung. Mathematical analysis has two main components: 1) Simple analysis done using a textual data analysis software (MAXQDA and NVivo, for example). These will be performed with the data from the open-ended questions and mainly consist of percentages of participant groups and answer groups or codes created ad hoc based on the answers obtained.

The second component of the mathematical analysis is represented by the analysis performed by the tool used to explore graphs and networks (e.g., Gephi) which searches for patterns in the structure of the networks inspected. The metrics analyzed include betweenness, centrality, closeness, and clustering of and among the different elements of the networks. The connection between social actors is calculated through analysis of in- and out-degrees, using basic matrix algebra via the software.

Körperliche Beanspruchung. In-person interactions will not exceed 2 (two) hours, in order not to cause participant's bodily or mental fatigue. Whenever logistically possible, water and snacks will be offered to the participants. Breaks will be offered throughout the interview, especially if it exceeds 1 (one) hour.

Online interactions should not exceed 1.5 (one and a half) hours, in order not to cause participant's bodily or mental fatigue. Breaks will be offered throughout the interview, especially if it exceeds 1 (one) hour.

For both the online and the in-person interactions, participants will be informed that they can pause the interview whenever they wish to do so.

Mentale Beanspruchung. In-person interactions will not exceed 2 (two) hours, in order not to cause participant's bodily or mental fatigue. Whenever logistically possible, water and snacks will be offered to the participants. Breaks will be offered throughout the interview, especially if it exceeds 1 (one) hour.

Online interactions should not exceed 1.5 (one and a half) hours, in order not to cause participant's bodily or mental fatigue. Breaks will be offered throughout the interview, especially if it exceeds 1 (one) hour.

For both the online and the in-person interactions, participants will be informed that they can interrupt the interview whenever they wish to do so.

Preisgabe persönlicher Informationen. The data collected consist mostly of the participants' perception of nature and of their relationships with the social (other actors) and ecological systems. Participants will also be asked their self-assigned gender, age, profession, organizations to which they are affiliated, village and city where they live, and degree of formal education. This is essential information for the tailoring of public engagement recommendations to the communication needs of the participants and the social groups they might represent.

Some organizations to be involved in this project can be relatively small, with only a few people working there. Still, the information collected will not allow for the identification of individual participants because, in the case that a combination of these personal details could point to a possible interviewee, one of these pieces of information will be excluded from specific analyses/datasets. For example, if an organization only has one female employee, the self-assigned gender might be kept in a subset that analyzes self-assigned gender of participants but **not** in combination with the organization to which they belong. This means that these subsets of the data would be stored without a code that could allow for a cross-referencing.

Täuschung und Aufklärung. No methods of deception will be employed when recruiting or interviewing participants. The scope, aims, and rationale of the research will be clearly detailed to those involved, as long as it does not lead to biased replies, with interviewees being provided an information sheet (below) and verbal explanation of the research prior to the commencement of the interview. Informed consent and use of a consent form (also see below) will be used.

5. Angaben zu Aufzeichnung, Aufbereitung, Speicherung und Löschung der Daten

Personenbezogene Daten. Name, organization, and village/city of origin will be collected but later anonymised. Other than self-assigned gender, age, village and city where they live, and degree of formal education, no personal information (name, address etc.) will be collected from the participants involved in the online or in-person interactions.

Datenschutz. Participants will be anonymized. If mentioned in publications, other markers will be used to describe the participant (such as profession and/or village of origin) but never in a way that might allow for their identification.

Kodierliste und persönliches Codewort. None.

Löschung der Daten. The recorded interviews will be destroyed as soon as interviews are transcribed and at the latest by the end of the project, 31.12.2024 by which point the collected data will have been interpreted and evaluated. The interpreted and analyzed data will

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be kept for at least 10 years. Participants can request all the data collected about them to be deleted, provided this request is made before the data are anonymized using the coding system described above. Participants will be informed about an estimation of this deadline.

6. Gewinnung der Personenstichprobe und Vergütung von Probanden

Rekrutierung. Relevant local actors in each study area will join as participants in this project. An initial list of potential participants will be based on previous studies, which identify relevant localities and organizations, and on previous interactions by the researchers and collaborators in this project with possibly relevant participants. A list of stakeholders will be drawn up and, once identified, potential participants will be approached via an appropriate channel – email or telephone – with the researchers' affiliations and details made overt and clear to potential interview subjects.

In case contact data have to be passed from one researcher/collaborator to another, this will only happen with previous consent by the possible participant. They will then be invited to participate in the interviews, either in-person or online.

Personenstichprobe aus Datenbank? Not applicable.

Merkmale der Personenstichprobe. Only interviewees relevant to the study will be identified, listed, and invited. The participants will all be over the age of 18 and will give written, informed consent.

Einschluss- und Ausschlusskriterien. Only interviewees relevant to the study will be identified, listed and invited. Potentially relevant participants are those who are, or would be expected to be, connected to local marine governance (at the level of each study case). Therefore, the connection to local marine governance as a criterion is of a *de facto* nature but also related to local regulations and resource use which should point to possible "interest groups" – therefore the importance of the literature review. Given the life span of the project, ample time will be allowed for contact to be made and interviews to take place, flexibly, based on the availability of the participant.

Internetbasierte Datengewinnung. Specifically for the case of the Weddell Sea (Antarctica), the construction of the social-ecological networks will be largely based on analysis of freely available documentation, such as treaties, laws, papers, news, etc. A large part of the dataset is composed by documents and data publicly available through the Commission for the Conservation of Antarctic Marine Living Resources (CCAMLR). Data use will follow CCAMLR's "Rules for Access and Use of CCAMLR Data", available at <https://www.ccamlr.org/en/data/data>.

This project might also attempt to obtain secondary data, from other research projects, but this will only happen for those studies where participants have previously agreed to have their data shared with other researchers for secondary analysis. This analysis of secondary

data might be complemented with elements of the interviews mentioned above, but this will depend on the data available.

Teilnahmevergütung. Participation is purely voluntary, and interviewees will not be financially compensated. Also, participants will not receive any sort of non-monetary compensation for their participation in this research. They will be explicitly informed of that and of the fact that this research is not directly related to the application of any sort of public or private policy and no direct benefits can be expected from its execution.

7. Freiwilligkeit der Teilnahme und Rücktritt

Freiwilligkeit. Participants of the interview will be provided with an information sheet (see below), detailing the scope, rationale, and objectives of the project. They will also be given a consent form (also see below). Whenever possible, these forms will be sent to participants at least one week prior to interview, so as to enable them to make an informed decision as to their participation. The forms will be translated into Portuguese (for the Brazilian case study). The aim, scope and rationale of the research will also be given to participants in both written and oral form by the researcher(s) at the time of the interview.

Rücktritt. It will be explained to participants both in writing (through the information and consent forms) and verbally at the start of interviews that they have the right to stop the interview at any time. They do not need to provide a reason. They will also have the possibility to request that their data is deleted after the interview has taken place, up until the point at which the data is anonymized using the coding system described above.

8. Informiertheit und Einwilligung

Informiertheit. As noted above, full information will be given to participants detailing the objectives, scope, and rationale of the research.

Einwilligung. For interviews, the consent form will stress that participation is voluntary, that participants have been fully informed about the research they are participating in, and that they can withdraw from the interview at any time during the interview without providing a reason. The consent form will require the signatures of participants.

Bild- und Tonaufnahmen. Interviews will be recorded (audio only). All recordings will be destroyed once the transcription process has been completed.

Oldenburg, 7.6.2022

Ort, Datum

Unterschrift Antragsteller

Declaration of Consent Form

Helmholtz Institute for Functional Marine Biodiversity (HIFMB)

Prof. Dr Kimberley Peters
HIFMB and Institute of Social Science

Dr. Rebecca Borges
HIFMB

Jonas Healy
HIFMB

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26129 Oldenburg
jonas.healy@hifmb.de
Phone: +49 176 3448 6319

Declaration of consent

The study is being carried out by the Marine Governance Working Group at the Helmholtz Institute for Functional Marine Biodiversity (HIFMB) and Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI), in cooperation with the Carl von Ossietzky University of Oldenburg.

Study title: Connectivity of Social Networks and Ecosystem Services for Transboundary Coastal-Marine Spatial Planning

I (name of participant in block capitals)

have been informed about the study via an information sheet and verbally before the interview. I consent to participation in the project outlined in the information sheet and verbally. Any questions I had about this study were answered completely and to my satisfaction by Dr Rebecca Borges.

Collection and processing of data

I agree to the described collection and processing of data, which takes the form of an interview. This data is recorded and evaluated at HIFMB, University of Oldenburg using a pseudonym, i.e. a number and without stating my name. There is a code list (hard copy) which can be used to link my name to this number. This code list is only accessible to the investigators and the project leader, i.e. only these persons can associate the collected data with my name. Once the data has been transcribed, the code list will be destroyed. My data will then be anonymous. As such, it will no longer be possible for anyone to associate the collected data with my name. I am aware that I can revoke my consent to the storage or retention of this data without this resulting in negative consequences for me.

I have been informed that I can request the deletion of all my data at any time. However, if the code list has already been destroyed, my dataset can no longer be identified and can therefore no longer be deleted. My data will then be anonymous. I agree that my anonymised data can be used for research purposes and will be stored for at least 10 years. I have been informed that my name is stated only on this declaration of consent. Also, data cannot be withdrawn after the publication of the results via scientific or policy-related means of communication, such as journals or policy briefs.

Audio recordings:

I am informed that audio recordings will be made. The audio recordings are made and evaluated anonymously. This can be done using a personal code word which I have created myself and which only I know or using a pseudonym, i.e. a number and without stating my name in combination with a code list (hard copy) which can be used to link my name to this number. The code list is only accessible to the lead investigator and is destroyed once the data has been collected and transcribed. For this reason, all persons involved in the evaluation are bound by professional secrecy and may under no circumstances pass on confidential information to third parties.

I am aware that I can revoke my consent to the storage or retention of this data without this resulting in negative consequences for me. The audio recording will be stored in a locked cabinet. I have been informed that I can request the deletion of all my data at any time, as long as the code list has not been destroyed. All recordings will be destroyed once the transcription process has been completed.

I am completing this consent form for audio recordings voluntarily. I can revoke this consent at any time during the interview. If I object or withdraw my consent, I will not incur any expenses or be disadvantaged in any other way; I will nevertheless/not be able to participate in the study.

I have had enough time to make a decision and am prepared to participate in the abovementioned study. I know that participation in the study is voluntary and that I can withdraw from the interview at any time without stating reasons.

I have received a copy of the information for participants regarding the examination and a copy of the declaration of consent. The information for participants forms part of this declaration of consent.

Place, date & signature of the participant:

Name of the participant in block letters:

Place, date & signature of the investigator:

Name of the lead investigator in block letters:

Infographic

A STUDY OF COMMUNICATION AND RELATIONSHIPS IN LOUGH FOYLE

WHO ARE WE?

HIFMB
OLDENBURG

- We are the marine governance group at the interdisciplinary Helmholtz Institute of Functional Marine Biodiversity (HIFMB)
- At HIFMB we investigate marine biodiversity and its importance for the function of coastal-marine ecosystems
- The marine governance group has a focus on social science and humanities approaches to marine biodiversity and ocean management

WHY ARE WE CONDUCTING THIS STUDY?

1. To understand connections between social actors and elements of the environment
2. To identify possible obstacles to successfully conserving biodiversity and sustaining people's livelihoods
 - a. The results of this study can be used to mitigate mismatches in assessing, planning, implementing, and monitoring conservation projects in the future

WHAT ARE THE METHODS WE ARE USING?

- Interviews with representatives of various stakeholder groups related to Lough Foyle
- To learn more about not only the communication and collaboration, but also the perceptions related to coastal-marine spaces and their governance among the social actors

VOLUNTARINESS AND DATA PROTECTION

- Interviews will be recorded for transcription, once transcribed they will become anonymous
- Participation is voluntary and you can withdraw from the study at any time before and during the interview
- Personal data collected will be treated confidentially and results from this study will be published anonymously

CONTACT ME

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E-Mail: jonas.healy@hifmb.de, Phone: +49 176 3448 6319

 ALFRED-WEGENER-INSTITUT
HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FÜR POLAR-
UND MEERESFORSCHUNG

 HIFMB
OLDENBURG

 Carl von Ossietzky
Universität
Oldenburg

Information sheet

We would like to invite you to our study on the “Connectivity of Social Networks and Ecosystem Services for Transboundary Coastal-Marine Spatial Planning”. This study is being carried out in the field of marine social sciences to assess how movements of people and of ecosystem services and boundaries affect social-ecological networks, or the way different people and groups communicate and collaborate for nature conservation.

Where is the study based?

The study is being conducted by the Marine Governance Working Group at Helmholtz Institute for Functional Marine Biodiversity (HIFMB), in Germany. Founded in 2017, the HIFMB is an institutional cooperation between the Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI), in Bremerhaven, and the Carl von Ossietzky University in Oldenburg. As an interdisciplinary research institute, it investigates marine biodiversity and its importance for the function of coastal- marine ecosystems.

Why are we conducting this study?

Understanding the different connections among people and between social actors and elements of the environment (for example, ecosystems) can give us subsidies to understand governance structures and identify possible obstacles to successfully conserving biodiversity and sustaining people’s livelihoods. This study will investigate if these networks constrain or enable key social processes and how multiple scales of action are linked.

The results of these analyses, complemented with an investigation of perceptions related to coastal-marine spaces and their governance, can be used to mitigate mismatches in assessing, planning, implementing, and monitoring conservation projects.

What are the methods of this research project?

Study sites

So far, this study has two main research sites. One of them is the Amazon coast, in north Brazil. The second site is Lough Foyle, shared by Northern Ireland (UK) and the Republic of Ireland.

Interviews

We would like to learn more about communication and collaboration among the various stakeholder groups that are related to Lough Foyle and the current management of the Lough. For that, we will conduct interviews with representatives of these groups. These interviews could be in-person or online and should last for about one hour.

We would like to record the audio of the interviews so that we can transcribe the conversation for future use in the research project. Once transcribed, the interview will also become **anonymous**.

If you have any further questions, please contact:

Jonas Healy, HIFMB Ammerländer Heerstraße 231, 26129, OL.
E-Mail: jonas.healy@hifmb.de, Phone: +49 176 3448 6319

Voluntary and anonymous

Participation in the study is voluntary. You may withdraw from this study at any time before or during the interview without giving a reason. There will be no negative consequences.

The personal data collected as part of this study (described above) will be treated confidentially. As such, project staff members who have access to your personal data as a result of direct contact with you are bound by professional secrecy. Furthermore, the results of the study will be published anonymously, i.e. it will not be possible to identify you from the data.

Data protection

The personal data mentioned above is collected and processed at HIFMB using a number and without stating your name. There is a code list (hard copy) which can be used to link your name to this number. This code list is only accessible to lead investigators and the project leader, i.e. only these persons can associate the collected data with your name. The code list is stored in a locked cabinet and once the data has been transcribed it will be destroyed. Your data will then be anonymous. As such, it will no longer be possible for anyone to associate the collected data with your name. The anonymous data will be kept for at least 10 years. As long as the code list has not been destroyed, you can request that all the data collected about you be deleted. Once the code list has been destroyed, however, we will no longer be able to identify your dataset. Therefore, we can only comply with your request to delete your data as long as the code list still exists. Also, data cannot be withdrawn after the data have been anonymized using the coding system described above.

Data Protection officer:

Patrick Rüscher
Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg
Der Datenschutzbeauftragte
Ammerländer Heerstraße 114 – 118 26129 Oldenburg
Tel.: +49 (0) 441 798 4196
E-Mail: dsuni@uol.de

Codesystem with main themes for the analysis of the interview transcripts

Liste der Codes	Häufigkeit
Codesystem	680
Importance	34
Oyster Fisheries	11
Boundaries	79
Transboundary issues	100
Information Dissemination	18
(Trans-boundary) MPA	17
Management of the Foyle	133
Ecological Features	57
Activities of Groups	73
Temporal markers	42
Brexit	34
Collaboration	82

Eidesstattliche Erklärung

Hiermit versichere ich an Eides statt, dass ich diese Arbeit selbstständig verfasst habe und keine anderen als die angegebenen Quellen verwendet, sowie keine unzulässige fremde Hilfe in Anspruch genommen habe. Zudem wurde die Arbeit nicht unter unkenntlichem Einsatz generativer KI erbracht. Außerdem versichere ich, dass ich die allgemeinen Prinzipien wissenschaftlichen Arbeitens und Veröffentlichens, wie sie in den Leitlinien guter wissenschaftlicher Praxis der Carl von Ossietzky Universität Oldenburg festgelegt sind, befolgt habe. Weiterhin erkläre ich, dass die Arbeit in gleicher oder ähnlicher Form noch keiner Prüfungsbehörde vorgelegt wurde.

Mir ist bekannt, dass eine eidesstattliche Versicherung eine nach den §§ 156, 161 Strafgesetzbuch (StGB) strafbewertete Bestätigung der Richtigkeit meiner Erklärung ist. Mir sind die strafrechtlichen Folgen einer unrichtigen, d.h. nicht den Tatsachen entsprechenden und unvollständigen Erklärung, d. h. das Verschweigen der wesentlichen Tatsachen bekannt.

Oldenburg, 07.07.2025

Jonas Healy